

Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT™

Work Based Research Masters Project by: Grant Van Ulbrich

Research Question: **“How do I explain change in a modern, simplistic, self-help model that incorporates personal choice and a support mechanism to see the change through?”**

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Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT

MSc Professional Practice in Leading Sales Transformation

Cover Sheet for Written Assignments

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Date: **December 15, 2020**

Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT

Module 7 Project Abstract Information

Name: Grant S. Van Ulbrich	
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Module Title: Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT: How do I explain change in a modern, simplistic, self-help model that incorporates personal choice and a support mechanism to see the change through?	
Project/Abstract title/Research question: "How do I explain change in a modern, simplistic, self-help model that incorporates personal choice and a support mechanism to see the change through?"	
Search words (List 5 key words relating to your project that people might use to find your abstract in an index) Change Model, Sales, Transformation, Fear	
Abstract – 100 - 200 words maximum	
<p>Change management models and leadership styles are not a one size fits all approach. This project shows how I was able to embrace aspects of Wilkinson's (2006) Generative leadership style through ambiguity and create my own change management model. Setting out with a clear vision, and creating my own model, as a strategy (Kotter 2012) reflects a leadership vs management style to ultimately help my sales team to learn how to navigate their feelings and emotions through personal change scenarios.</p> <p>SCARED – SO WHAT initially was designed to help my sales team and leadership in successfully launching a new sales academy for our cruise brands in the Royal Caribbean Group. It is when a much larger, unexpected change process occurred in the middle of this project, that this model began to help employees and myself in navigating the change process in a much simpler, easy to understand way.</p> <p>At the end of this research project, I have uncovered favorable recommendations for the SCARED-SO WHAT model and believe that it has a future in helping people around the world in navigating personal change. "Change is constant – how you navigate the change makes it bearable and achievable" (Van Ulbrich, 2020).</p>	
I am happy for my project abstract to be shared with: (please tick)	
My company	<input type="checkbox"/>
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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1. PREAMBLE

Throughout my research project many people asked me right off the bat, “Why did you feel the need to create another change model?” It is funny to me that people start off with that question, but once I explain it to them, then they see it the same way I did.

In my organisation, I have become known as a builder of departments and projects. At Royal Caribbean Group, we have just over 75,000 employees spanning the globe serving our guests memorable vacation experiences each day. My personality is one of curiosity and I am always asking myself how we can do it better. That curiosity has led me to create the industry’s first office of Diversity & Inclusion with over 3,000 employees participating in employee groups in making us a better place to work. It’s also led me to completely overhaul our onboard future cruise program where we had just one-person onboard selling future cruises to guests, to now having the most luxurious and profitable travel centers onboard our combined fleet, generating in excess of \$1B annually during normal business times outside of a global pandemic. That same curiosity led me to start a new department of Sales Transformation and led me to this master’s program where I am now able to help transform our sales teams and champion their personal and professional development.

But why a new change model? Simply put, the others were not for me. My same sense of curiosity led me to ask, where is the change model that is designed to help me navigate my own personal change? Most models I see and am introduced to are for organizations to use on me to champion their own change needs. But they do not ask me my own feelings, rather they assume that I am going to feel or behave in a certain way. Where is my own personal choice being considered in these models to guide me in my own feelings towards the change? And yet, I am supposed to execute the change for them? There is a gap, and the gap is that I believe these prescriptive models aren’t designed to help me with my needs.

1.2. AND THE PURPOSE OF THIS RESEARCH IS?

The purpose of this research is to review and share my new personal change model SCARED-SO WHAT™ with others inside and outside of my organization, in hopes of finding out if the model is simple, helpful, and usable by others.

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At the core of the model, I have built in the user’s ability to choose and recognize their own feelings instead of prescribing the outcome. “Change is personal, and change is constant. How you navigate change makes it bearable and achievable,” (Van Ulbrich, 2020). I challenged the current models as being prescriptive and assuming that I am going to behave or make a certain choice towards favorability. That does not work for me. I believe a person has the right to choose and SCARED-SO WHAT™ allows for that personal choice to happen and yet help them in navigating personal change.

1.3. OVERVIEW OF THIS PROJECT

In chapter two, I will look at the terms of reference where this project and research comes from. I will then focus on the aims and objectives of the work-based research project and then discover what the literature review shows regarding change models.

Chapter three will give insight into the approach I have taken as an insider researcher and a look at what my methodology and methods of conducting this project will include. I will uncover the research questions that I have asked if the new personal change model SCARED-SO WHAT is, in reference to being simple, helpful and usable by others.

Chapter three also takes us through quantitative and qualitative data collection and what exactly they mean towards this research. In this chapter I will also look at how I defined my role as an insider researcher and talk about duality and reflexivity and what that means. And throughout the chapters, I will also talk about ethics and the importance of recognizing bias.

Chapter four is where I will uncover the data collection process and research actions taken. It is here where I will uncover the interviews and how they were conducted. I will also look at the surveys, where, and how they were conducted. Finally, in this chapter, I will delve into reflection on the research process and the actions taken.

In chapter five I will go deep into what the data is telling. I will look at what it means to take a deductive approach and utilize thematic analysis as ways of analyzing data. It is here where the data begins to tell the answers to my research questions and gives clues as to what the future of this model might be all while discussing ethics and bias as well.

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Chapter six is where I look at critical reflection on the overall project. I will also review the recommendations and outcomes for the new personal change model and discuss the potential favorability and use for the model going forward. And it is here where I look at an unexpected outcome of the new model to be used perhaps as a coaching tool.

But first, before I get all the way through to the end, I want to look next into chapter two on the terms of reference, the project's aims and objectives and what the literature review reveals.

CHAPTER 2: RATIONALE, TERMS OF REFERENCE, QUESTIONS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. RATIONALE

By October of 2019, I had already completed module three of the MSc program with Consalia (2019) and had begun module four on Leading Collaborative Change. Simultaneously, at Royal Caribbean Group, in my role of leading Sales Transformation for the international sales teams, I had just completed launching the first learning pathway in our new digital sales training program called SPARK¹. The master’s program and Consalia were helping me to shape the sales training of the future for my sales teams in Europe, Middle East and Africa and soon to be to other global regions.

Whilst beginning module four within the master’s program, I noticed that the adoption rate and utilization of SPARK was not happening with the speed and acceptance that I had anticipated. “Why were the teams not using the program,” was a question I pondered night and day. Bassot’s (2016) teaching on reflection in and on action were helping me to uncover this mystery by continuing to think and reflect on my actions taken to lead the teams. It would only be through module four of the masters on Leading Collaborative Change, that I would be able to uncover the possible answer to my question.

During module four, we focused heavily on change and the causes and effects with variable change models to include the SARA Curve, (Rogel 2010) Connor’s (2012) Positive Change Cycle, Kotter’s (2014) 8 Accelerators model and many more. My “ah ha” moment came during those classes. Brown, Heyer and Ettenson (2013) articulated it best by stating “...not being able to articulate why the project is being done, puts it at risk of losing support and momentum and decreases its chance of success.” I readily identified with that statement in the fact I failed to explain why our sales leaders needed to launch the SPARK program for and with their teams during that time. In failing to explain the why, they went on as normal with the attitude of “we’ll get to it when we get to it.” I had later confirmed this by speaking with each of the leaders.

¹ SPARK stands for Sales, Performance, Action, Resource, and Knowledge.

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Suspecting why it failed, I was left searching for a way to explain the change process and bring them along on the journey. I was very conflicted with the change models we learned about. To me, they all appeared prescriptive towards a negative action and not providing personal choice or ability to fluctuate between negative and positive energy. In addition to that, the models appeared to be leaning more towards organizational change, except for Kübler-Ross’ change curve, which was designed to support a specific change in one’s life – the acceptance of their (Kübler-Ross 2020) impending death. I did not agree with the current models in their prescriptive meaning. My professor challenged me to create my own model. And so, I did. I began to sketch out my own model for change with reflections on what I had just learned and that would include an individual’s ability to choose their own path. My instructors provided me critical time to think (Kline 2018) and I created a new change model and a working theory for personal use and self-understanding. I named that change theory SCARED-SO WHAT^{TM2} (See Appendix A). The major reason I did this is to understand if my new model, that I had designed to help people navigate Personal Change, could in fact be helpful and useful and effective in achieving that goal. If people could easily understand what they are experiencing during a Personal Change event, then perhaps it would be easier for them to make their own So What plan to navigate the change occurrence.

2.1.1. WHY AM I CONCERNED?

As much as I intended for my search to yield critical reviews of the major change models that exist today, my search for personal change models pulled me into the broad spectrum of organizational and developmental change management with a strong focus on business needs. The focus, I had found, is almost entirely embedded and deeply rooted into change management to drive organizational change; and was not generally focused on the persons involved and their own personal change, but more so on how to execute and facilitate change for organizations at large. In his *Change Management Models: A Comparative Analysis and Concerns* review, Joseph Galli (2018) said “Change is inevitable, whether it is personal or professional.” Creasy (2018) stated that CM is “the application of a structured

² SCARED-SO WHAT is my working theory on a new personal change management model. I have filed to trademark the name and copyright the 1st working version.

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process and set of tools for leading the people side of change to achieve a desired business outcome.”

Rune Todnem (2005) documented his work titled *Organizational Change Management: A Critical Review* and cited Balogun and Hope Hailey's (2004) work that “...the management of organisational change currently tends to be reactive...ad hoc, with a reported failure rate of around 70 per cent of all change programmes initiated.”

These statements concerned me greatly in the fact that if one follows the key words they reference, you would see their focus was on organisational / developmental change for the company; and did not focus on the person that needs to execute the change. The words “business outcome”, “management”, “organisation”, were the key words directing their focus. How is a person required to execute change when we are not focusing their personal change needs? The people themselves need to buy into the change, accept it, reject it, understand what their part and role will be to execute it. I believe we were missing that piece which may contribute to why 70 per cent (Balogun and Hope Hailey 2004) of change programs fail.

2.2. TERMS OF REFERENCE / SCOPE

My aim was to understand if my new model, SCARED-SO WHAT™ could be useful and effective to support the individual in understanding and navigating personal change, either at work, or for personal and situational use outside of work. I did this by disseminating the model to people by putting it out to our employees and to others externally for test and review. As Grant (2014) references, “The more you give, the more you want to do it – as do others around you.” Kurt Lewin also states, “People support what they create,” (Graban and Swartz, 2013). These are key ingredients as I wanted to give the models to others thus allowing them to support the creation and evolution of the SCARED-SO WHAT™ model. My main objectives in doing this research was to achieve the following:

- Package the model into a user-friendly digestible presentation.
- Engage my employee base in reviewing, usefulness, and feedback.
- Introduce externally to my travel partner base for usefulness and feedback.
- Get the model published in a professional journal.

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- Collect data responses both quantitative and qualitative to assess feasibility and usefulness and or to change and adapt the model.

By performing these objectives, I should have been able to assess feedback and incorporate into my final project dissertation and next steps. In leading change, a leader creates the vision and strategy for the team to manage and create plans and actions to achieve the end goal. (Kotter, 2012).

2.3. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

My questions asked, is the model helpful, or how does the model need to evolve and or change itself to maximize usefulness? In designing and enhancing this new change model, I used Gibbs (1988) Reflective Cycle to go back and revisit my feelings when I created the SCARED-SO WHAT™ model. I reflected on the fact I did not find the other models useable, or practical for inclusion of one's own ability to choose. I deduced that they were too prescriptive. My analysis led me to create my own model and my conclusion was the outcome with the SCARED-SO WHAT™ model as a working theory.

The aims and objectives that I had chosen would provide evidence to potentially uncover those same feelings that I had when creating the model. My own curiosity led me to challenge the current models in hope of an easier process to explain change to others. I remained open that other findings may occur and that the evidence may lead me to an altogether different thought process.

These feelings of curiosity are reflected below in three core areas of the model being simple, helpful, and useable to the end user and form my research questions below.

SIMPLE:

- How would you rate the model in relation to ability to use? (Scale 0-5)
- Please try to state what each of the letters mean?

HELPFUL:

- Do you feel the SCARED model could help you navigate your feelings during a change process? If yes, explain how. If no, explain why not?

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- Do you feel the SO WHAT model could help you build your own plan to facilitate or execute a change process? If yes, explain how. If no, explain why not?

USEABLE:

- If you were to use this model on others, how would you use it?
- How would you use this model for yourself?
- What changes would you recommend for usability of the model?

2.4. LITERATURE REVIEW

My literature review helped to shape my research on the effectiveness of the SCARED-SO WHAT™ model, by supporting the basis of reasoning of why it was necessary to be created in the first place. My hypothesis was that the current range of change models that were being promoted in contemporary organizations were not intentionally designed to focus on the employee of whom is expected to execute the required change. I did not believe that the current models I had been exposed to are effective in their ability to support the individual, experiencing the change occurring in themselves, let alone the change required of them.

To begin my literature review, I started by organizing my thoughts on where the focus of my research would warrant the best possible results. I started my plan, centering on two questions, of what my search would include and exclude (See Figure 2A). I also chose to search from 1985 to present day for reviews of change models representing a 35-year coverage.

Figure 2A: Search Criteria

What words will I search for?	What category is it Why?	Is there a date range?	What did I find?	Comments or specific notes?	
Key Words and Phrases	Category	Justification?	Time Frame	Results	Notes
What won't I search for?	What category is it Why?	Is there a date range?	What did I find?	Comments or specific notes?	
Key Words and Phrases	Category	Justification?	Time Frame	Results	Notes

My target focus was on the person experiencing change. I called this ‘Personal Change’, and I was not focused on organizational change, nor corporations, nor the vast array of processes known as Change Management or CM³. I was specifically focusing my research

³ CM is the professional designation for Change Management.

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on the reviews of existing models that have been built to facilitate change and may fall under the array of CM. In doing so, this narrowed down the availability of research and focused the scope of literature and data that I could use to analyze and support my research. I utilized Google Scholar and the Middlesex University Library to perform my searches. (See Appendix B and C).

2.4.1. MODELS FOR CHANGE:

My search criteria discovered 3 applicable results for reviews of change management models and yielded an abundance of general results for use of the major models with most focused towards organisational change management in variable fields of work and study (See Figure 2B).

Figure 2B: Search Criteria

Medium	Justification?	Time Frame	Results
Middlesex University Library Online	Focus is on specific models that a person can use on themselves for understanding and actioning individual change.	1985-2020	<p>"Change Management Models" brought 273 results and found 1 comparative review that focused on change models themselves.</p> <p>"Change Models" brought 16,336 results and after skimming through the first 50 pages, I could not find anything relative to a model review or critique. The masses were on climate change, health change, and theory.</p> <p>"Models for Change" brought 149 results and after skimming through the first 50 pages, I could not find anything relative to a model review or critique. The masses were varied from healthcare to energy, to climate change.</p> <p>"Review of Change Models" brought 1 result which was an Organizational change models and digital library project review. Had nothing to reflect on actual change models.</p>
Google Scholar - Searched here and then went to Middlesex University Library online to avoid paying for any relevant articles or sources.	Focus is on specific models that a person can use on themselves for understanding and actioning individual change.	1985-2020	<p>"Change Management Models" brought 2,350 results and found 2 items. One interesting doctoral thesis, one comparative analysis, and many that were not relevant as they related to changing organizations themselves.</p> <p>"Change Models" brought 35,500 results and after skimming through the first 50 pages, I could not find anything relative to a model review or critique. The masses were on structures, mathematics, land surface, environmental and various organizational change.</p> <p>"Models for Change" brought 7,110 results and after skimming through the first 50 pages, I could not find anything relative to a model review or critique. The masses were varied from logistics, transition, technology, education and healthcare change.</p> <p>"Review of Change Models" brought 32 results which brought together doctoral thesis papers and studies from general change management, business change, leader behavior inventory, digital and educational change but not the review of change models I was looking to find.</p>

As a result, the models that I chose to focus from the critical reviews were Kurt Lewin’s Change Theory (See Appendix D), Kotter’s Eight Stage Process (See Appendix E), ADKAR (See Appendix F), McKinsey 7-S model (See Appendix G), the Change Curve from Elisabeth Kübler-Ross (See Appendix H). I also included my own review of the SARA Curve (See

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Appendix I) which is considered an adaptation of Elisabeth Kübler-Ross's Change Curve, and I included Connor's Positive Change Cycle (See Appendix J). These were what I personally considered to be my top 7 models of preference for managing change. Figure II: Search Results

2.4.2. WHAT IS IT THAT CONCERNS ME?

When I started to review deeply between each critique, I began to formulate an observation that perhaps we were trying to use all models for all things. That simply cannot be done. Schech-Storz (2013) surmises that "...not all changes are the same; therefore, management needs to use different change models and methodologies depending on the situation." Although, Mr. Lewin might not agree, Joseph Galli (2019) further stated a disadvantage of Lewin's Change Theory is that it doesn't deal with the human part of the change, and Kotter's Eight Stages model is most limited on the people aspect. He further directs that this is the common limitation of most change models and methods.

"ADKAR has the greatest employee or person focus", said Joseph Galli (2019). ADKAR (Hiatt 2006) can be focused on the individual personal journey for change, as am I, but does not go as far to explain or guide you in finding what you can do to execute the change. Joseph Galli further states that it is "limited when seeking large-scale implementations." As a result, he concluded that one must understand the choices of the models available as a first step. "However, be aware that the model itself can be perfect for the organisation or company, but without the willingness or desire to change from employees and team members, the process to implement change will almost always fail."

In Mulholland's (2017) *8 Critical Change Management Models to Evolve and Survive*, he praises Lewin's model when your business needs to drastically change. But he cautions "...if you're not careful the disruption can alienate your employees." Lewin himself supported that statement when "Lewin postulates that even with desirable goals, resistance to change is common. For a change to be effective, replacing organisational behaviours and attitudes must reinforce it." (Todnem 2005).

When reviewing McKinsey's 7-S model, Mulholland (2017) surmised the model is great when you are wanting to expose the weaknesses in a company. And he thought that it

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was the model best suited for those companies who want to know how they can make changes for the better. That is great in my opinion, but it left me asking “What about the employees themselves?” Mulholland (2017) and Joseph Galli (2019) both concurred that Kotter’s Eight Stages model is beneficial, but it comes across as a “top-down approach” said both in their separate reviews. They further stated that “...employees do not have input.” For this, the obvious gap is that these models are not designed to support the employee or individual with processing change for themselves. I saw it as, I am talking at you and telling you what you must change, vs. helping you to internalize the change itself so you can facilitate it.

My concern was further reinforced with Rune Todnem’s (2005) work titled ‘*Organisational Change Management: A Critical Review*’ was relevant in where he argues that “...theories and approaches to change management currently available to academics and practitioners are often contradictory, mostly lacking empirical evidence and supported by unchallenged hypotheses concerning the nature of contemporary organisational change management.” It was relevant in the fact that the entire search process led me to conclude that change models are associated if not deeply rooted into organisational change management but not for the individual themselves.

I would be remiss if I did not include Connor’s Positive Change Model (2012) in where he states, “Change is easy when people like it.” I enjoyed this model because Conner is intentionally focused on the individual and therefore supporting them on their journey. He hypothesizes that the individual going through the positive change would go through a process of uninformed optimism, informed pessimism where afterwards they may check out but then he shows they go through hopeful realism, and informed optimism before they get to completion. I can appreciate that as he is forecasting a positive change. But what if the change is unknown or negative or neutral? Conner (2012) then provides a similar model which he shares is an extension of the Kübler-Ross Change Curve in where he reflects sometimes people hate the change.

Elisabeth Kübler-Ross’s (2020), *The 5 Stages of Grief* led to her *Change Curve* and was created to help people when processing thoughts and feelings when dealing with their own impending situation on death and dying. Mulholland (2017) gives a critique of Ross’s model but right from the beginning I lose credibility with this one critique. He wrote, it is a

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“checklist” and references multiple times the changes the “employee” will go through. He praises it for anticipating and managing the emotional reactions, but then criticizes the model for not “providing a method for guiding employees through each stage.” I believe It was not written for employees.

It is hard to blame him for his critique as the Kübler-Ross Change Curve has been adapted over the years and condensed into the SARA Curve (Rogel 2010). Since beginning this journey on change and change models, I still cannot find when or who blatantly changed her model into the SARA Curve. All references of SARA or SARAH Curve give credit back to Mrs. Kübler-Ross.

In this instance, Rogel’s (2010) scenario applied the Sara Curve directly towards a business setting where a person might process the response to a 360-degree employee review. In my opinion, this was rather one sided as it was insinuating that the review is going to be negative and not a positive experience. But there you have it – people will adapt models as to how they see fit, which means they potentially are searching for help or support. I see the SARA Curve referenced abundantly – although notably misguided as for the need for a misconceptions page about Kübler-Ross’s change curve model also known as ‘*The 5 Stages of Grief.*’ (Kessler 2020).

2.5. SUMMARY: HOW DOES THIS SHAPE MY VISION?

My research in reviewing the published literature confirmed my feelings that I had that same day, sitting in the master’s class, thoroughly confused at how these models were supposed to provide comprehensive guidance for individuals in dealing with personal change. My duty in leading sales transformation is to help transform or change my sales organisation for the best they can be. However, the models themselves appear to be mostly designed for the benefit of the organisation and not necessarily the people.

Joseph Galli (2018), Mulholland (2017), Todnem (2005), all reference that change will most definitely fail if due focus on the individual, is not made the primary focus. Van De Ven and Sun, (2011) critically review the breakdowns of change and state “Change agents typically respond to these breakdowns by taking actions to **CORRECT** people....so they conform to their model of change.” That right there says all I need to know.

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My vision with creating the SCARED-SO WHAT™ model might be justified to support the individual on their journey of personal change, in understanding what is happening to them, so they can make their own plan of action about how to action the change. My goal was and still is to champion their need. And it may very well prove beneficial to organizations as well, for use with one of these other existing models. I believe the literature confirms if we want change to work, then it must include the individual’s need and not just the organizations themselves.

In conclusion, this review has helped me to understand that there may be a need for a new model for ‘Personal Change’ that needs to be available at the onset of change to the individual. I believe that a person needs to be able to help themselves first to understand change before they can be in any position or frame of mind to accept and implement organisational change. My focus for the SCARED-SO WHAT™ model is towards the individual as a self-discovery methodology.

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CHAPTER 3: APPROACH, METHODOLOGY, METHODS AND ETHICS

Having reviewed my literature and confirmed my research questions, in this next chapter I discuss my approach in how I will conduct the research. Likewise, I share the methodology as well as the methods I intended to use to conduct my research in gathering the data necessary for critical analysis.

3.1. APPROACH

My work-based project approach included a blended mix of action research from McNiff (2017), and that of reflection from Gibb's (1988) Reflective Cycle. (See Figure 3A). This is an approach that relates to my own ontological perspective in how I formulate and conduct my own work practice daily. This supports the context of: "What is it that I am focusing on?", and "So What does this mean to me", along with "Now what will I do with or about it?", as a way of formulating and conducting my research.

Figure 3A: McNiff and Gibb blended approach

Additionally, I practiced the two main dominant research positions to include a Positivist and Interpretivist approach. (Costley, Elliott and Gibbs, 2010). The positivist approach includes observable and measurable facts using methods from natural science i.e. people as objects of research. The Positivist approach tends to be more quantitative data.

The Interpretivist approach gathers data about language, ideas, feelings, and meanings from people as participants. This is qualitative data and is subject to emotional bias of the insider researcher.

Both approaches complement my blended use of McNiff and Gibbs' views on action research and stem or flow from my ontological position namely, as well as my epistemological views that there is more to be known about the ability for an individual to navigate personal change.

For this research to be inclusive, I could not rely solely on the data from my internal working environment. Including persons outside of my work and immediate influence would

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be critical in providing evidence. My inquiry from the outside (Brannick and Coghlan, 2007), would entail to include persons through LinkedIn, and my Travel Agent community.

3.2. METHODOLOGY & METHODS

The main difference between methodology and methods is that methods are the steps, processes, and tactics that a person will use to conduct research (Adina 2016). The way I interpreted this difference was that it could be related to a cooking recipe. The recipe is the methodology. The actions conducted inside the recipe are the methods. The outcome of the recipe is the result. In summation, if you leave out one of the methods (steps in the recipe), your methodology (recipe)...might be flawed.

My methodology included action research (McNiff 2017), reflective practice (Gibbs 1988) and was shaped by positivist and interpretivist positions. (Costley, Elliott and Gibbs, 2010). I also conducted survey-based research as an insider-researcher. While there were a wide array of methodologies and approaches such as Ethnographic research, Grounded Theory, Case Study, and Bricolage approaches, (Costley, Elliott and Gibbs, 2010), I preferred that of action and survey-based research, and would better suit my own personal style and needs in conducting my research. The methods I utilized would be done so in as to find answers to my working theory and would include virtual, one-on-one discussions-as-interviews, (Costley, Elliott and Gibbs, 2010), and e-surveys, internally with our employees and a few hand selected external peers. I would utilize the survey tool Qualtrics both internally and externally via email. I had created a website to host the SCARED-SO WHAT information and would use that as a method of expressing the Scared-So What model online. People would review the models on the website www.scaredsowhat.com before the interview or survey was conducted and then feedback of the model would be collected.

My main objectives would support my project and at the end of this research I would know, understand, and or be in a better place to be able to:

- Package the model into a user-friendly digestible presentation.
- Have evidence of support from employees and peers of the model’s viability
- Ascertain if the model needs adjustment or enhancement
- Provide evidence of support from the general community my aim is to serve

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In leading change, a leader creates the vision and strategy for the team to manage and create plans and actions to achieve the end goal. (Kotter, 2012). By working towards my objectives, I should have been able to gather both qualitative and quantitative data for analysis and review of the model in creating a change process that has the potential to support others in achieving their personal end goal.

Given the current restraints of the Covid-19 pandemic, my research methods would need to be conducted via web or telephony methods as we were required to work from home. That said, should the quarantine had been lifted, then the same research could have been conducted in person where permitted. I would focus primarily on quantitative (numbers of interviews and data from survey responses) and qualitative (content of interviews and analysis of survey responses) collected.

3.2.1. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

My questions stemmed from my curiosity to find out if the models themselves, as they were, or as they needed to evolve, would be helpful for an individual to navigate a personal change scenario. The objectives that I had chosen would provide evidence to answer my research questions.

The research questions below were devised into three categories to identify if the models themselves were (in the user’s perspective) simple, helpful, and useable for navigating a personal change scenario.

To review the research questions utilized in this research, please refer to chapter 2.3 Research Questions pp13-14.

3.2.2. DATA COLLECTION – QUALITATIVE VS QUANTITATIVE

My methods of data collection would include the below items and whether they were defined as qualitative or quantitative (Costley, Elliott and Gibbs, 2010). Qualitative data would avail to uncover the supporting evidence that would shape and formulate the research questions to support the main objectives of this research project. Quantitative data would avail to uncover the number of responders that participated in my research project and would show evidence of numerical inclusion points.

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Method:	Metric:
Online, virtual web-based interviews	Qualitative
Telephony interviews	Qualitative
If permitted post Covid-19, in person interviews	Qualitative
Qualtrics Online Surveys (Anonymous)	Quantitative

3.2.3. INTERVIEWS: (N=15)

Flick (2018, p.209) references to Rubin and Rubin (2012, p.29) as defining interviews to be “outlining interviews as ‘in-depth qualitative interviewing’ which is characterized by three features.” The features include “rich and detailed information, not for yes-or-no, agree-or-disagree responses”. “Questions will be open-ended, and the order or arrangement of the questions are not in any fixed order. When conducting the interview, the questions can flow as they way of the conversation.”

Interviews are a beneficial way to obtain qualitative data that a survey would not be able to ascertain. As such, I conducted interviews as a method of obtaining qualitative data. I provided the prospect the appropriate research participation introduction from my approved MORE form and sought the interviewees permission to be interviewed and whether they wished to be identified or not. I did not reveal nor disclose anyone’s identity or responses without their expressed documented permission. I sought to obtain a blended mix of both internal and external interviews. My goal was to seek a minimum of 10 interviews via virtual setting.

3.2.4. SURVEYS: (N=43)

It is difficult to give a concise definition of a survey as many studies in of themselves have been labeled as surveys. (Robson 2002). Robson further states the typical central features of a survey are:

- The use of a fixed, quantitative design.
- The collection of a small amount of data in standardized form from a relatively large number of individuals.

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- The selection of representative samples of individuals from known populations.

Robson (2002, p.230) also shares this reference and credits Bryman (1989) with the following definition: 'Survey research entails the collection of data on a number of units and usually at a single juncture in time, with a view to collecting systematically a body of quantifiable data in respect of a number of variable s which are then examined to discern patters of association' (p. 104).

For my research, surveys would be beneficial in collecting quantifiable data about my research questions. They were conducted via the university's Qualtrics system and were done blindly. I included the appropriate introduction from the MORE form that by participating in the survey, the participant agreed their responses may be included in the data collection, but their identity will not be recorded, tracked, nor exposed without permission.

Internal Surveys: My goal was to reach approximately 170 respondents of either recently employed, or currently employed within my internal employee base. I included recently employed, as we had just concluded a large layoff of staff during Covid-19 that made up a large portion of my work stream. I guided them to think of how Covid-19 has had an effect of personal change and then use the model. From there, I asked their feedback with my set of questions.

I hypothesized that the recently employed group may have used the entire model in helping them to absorb the personal change scenario of being made redundant and formulating a plan to find another job. I also hypothesize that the currently employed group may have used only the first part of the model to accept or study the personal change that Covid-19 was having on their current livelihood. Being still employed at that moment, they may not have delved deeper into the SO WHAT part of the model. The interviews and surveys helped to uncover the similarities of usefulness or exposed any opportunity for usefulness of the models.

External Surveys: My goal was to reach 50 respondents within the context of using surveys via LinkedIn, Facebook, Professional Colleagues outside of the RCL organisation. Like the internal surveys, I would guide them to think of how Covid-19 has had an effect of

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personal change and then use the model. From there, I would ask their feedback with my set of questions.

I hypothesized that the external group may have needed time to utilize and reflect on the entire model, but they may have been able to readily identify with the SCARED portion. I would further be able to analyze the differences in responses between the internal and external survey results and would seek to find patterns or anomalies between them.

Email: Information provided by email would be scrubbed of all personal identifiable information according to the guiding principles of GDPR and MORE unless expressed documented permission is granted by the email correspondent.

3.3. RESEARCHER ROLE

3.3.1. MY POSITION:

My research position would be that of an insider-researcher and my ontological perspective would be through subjectivism; also known as interpretivism (Dudovskiy, 2016). Subjectivism and interpretivism are types of research approaches that are socially constructed, subjective, and may change. (Dudovskiy, 2016). This fit well within my own perception of myself, as I enjoy formulating my opinions by including other thoughts as well. Their thoughts and opinions would become inclusive of my data collection process of being quantitative and qualitative information. My epistemology would invite critique of the models and therefore reveal its potential truth, belief, and justification for working.

3.3.2. DUALITY / REFLEXIVITY:

The current challenge of my project was that I am an employee, championing other employees, and can influence change. I would need to continue my daily role but also function as an inquirer and a participant observer in the goal to “...bring about actual change.” (Costley, Elliott and Gibbs, 2010). Likewise, I would need to keep a keen sense of awareness of my own bias towards making the new model work. I would maintain my learning diary within action research so that I could reflect on what was happening during the process of my research.

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3.4. STRENGTHS & WEAKNESSES

The strengths of being an insider researcher and using interviews as well as surveys facilitated the ability to obtain both qualitative and quantitative data sets. These data sets would derive from groups to include current and recent former employees, and a select section of external peers, and their perspectives and views on the models. Additionally, I was able to obtain data from these subgroups in a quantitative data set that would help to identify the usefulness of the model.

The weaknesses included that I may ultimately bring in my own internal bias in analyzing the data and could potentially unknowingly shift that data analysis towards favoring the model, as its creator. To combat that potential outcome, I sought to attain support from persons in reviewing the data that have no ownership and include their individual analysis to that of my own. I would also be willful and accepting of the outcome of the data regardless of favor or unfavorable view of the usefulness of the model. A negative review may have also provided valuable insight in how to adjust or transform the model to better serve others.

3.5. ETHICS

Ranjan Kumar (2013) references Holihan (1999) where he asserts that “ethical issues are very sensitive since the IARr⁴ may have a history of working relationship with the members of the researched world”. This is significant and important for me to note as the research I have conducted during this project is with members of my organisation and some of whom are supervisors, and some are colleagues that I will continue to work with on an ongoing basis.

Rangan Kumar (2013) also tells us that “IARrs do not just perform the dual role of being researchers and employees. As the initiators and the champions of change in their organization, they have to perform multiple roles – a coach, a disciplinarian, a team builder, a teacher – besides those of being a researcher and an employee.”

⁴ IARr is the acronym for Insider action research (IAR) that is undertaken by professionals in their own organization. (Ranjan Kumar, 2013)

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During this research project, I functioned as an inside-researcher conducting action research while working within people’s thoughts, feelings, and perceptions while undertaking and utilizing the SCARED-SO WHAT model.

As Costley, Elliott and Gibbs, (2010) say, “...all research is subject to criticism,” it behooves me to put aside my own bias in favor towards my model and ensure that I remain open to the input and consideration of others.

During this research project I followed all aspects of GDPR as well as the university’s MORE process of which I had submitted and received approval from the university to pursue as part of my research. I followed my personal, professional, company, and university ethics and ensured that no sensitive or un-permitted information was relayed or publicized without express written consent. The challenge will be to continue to maintain these ethical standards as I continue working with my organisation post research and continuing onward.

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CHAPTER 4: RESEARCH ACTIONS – DATA COLLECTION

Action research is where real people evaluate their practice taking on the view that they can improve it (McNiff 2017). I had incorporated action research with an interpretivist approach into my role as an insider researcher (Dudovskiy, 2016).

I chose the interpretivist approach because this type of research approach incorporates actions and methods that are socially constructed, subjective, and may change (Dudovskiy, 2016). Within this, I could identify with research in a socially constructed methodology as it is the same characteristic in the way I choose and prefer to work with my team and others.

My aim was to uncover whether the new personal change model SCARED-SO WHAT™, could have the potential to be simple, helpful and or usable, with the individual participant. In this chapter, we will discuss the data planning, methods and processes used, and finally my reflection on the experience.

4.1. PLANNING FOR DATA COLLECTION AND METHODS

I began my data collection during the chapter 3 process of module 7 in the master’s program in June of 2020. In search of an aid to support the data collection, I came upon an Excel based tool I discovered online from GradCoach.com (Jansen 2020), (See figure 4A).

Figure 4A: Grad Coach Excel Research Data Collection Tool.

Author	Year	Title	Category 1	Category 2	Category 3	Document type	Publication setting	Knowledge type	Key
David Kessler	2020	Grief: Misconceptions	Sara Curve	Change Model		Webpage	Academic	Empirical	Mo
EKR Foundation	2020	Change Curve	Sara Curve	Change Model		Webpage	Academic	Empirical	Th
Andrew H. Van De Ven, K. Sun	2011	Breakdowns in implementing models of organization change.	Change Models somewhat	Organization change mostly		Webpage	Academic	Empirical	Pa
Daryl Connor	2012	Change is Easy when people like it.	Change Model	Positive Change		Book	Academic	Empirical	Po
M. Graban / J. Swartz	2013	Healthcare Kaizen: Engaging Front-Line Staff in Sustainable Continuous Improvement	Change Improvement	Change Leader	Change Quote	Book	Academic	Empirical	Fre
Kotter, J.	2012	Leading Change	Leading Change	Leadership	Change Model	Book	Academic	Empirical	B

This tool supported me throughout my literature review and from there, I was able to add on extra worksheet tabs to plan, structure, and capture my data into one trackable data warehouse.

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My two chosen methods for data collection included semi-structured interviews in a qualitative fashion and surveys as a quantitative measure (Robson 2002). Semi-structured interviews allow for a medium structure to be incorporated into them and focus on open questions to prompt the interviewee for data points. They also permit for flexibility in the conversation at the discretion of the interviewer and interviewee. I thought of this as a free-flowing conversation with guiding points along the way with key awareness on introduction, content, time, and attention towards the interviewee.

The surveys were scripted with open ended questions and were conducted online via Qualtrics and prepared with the use of the Middlesex University system for data recording. The surveys would complement the semi-structured interviews by adding in quantitative data that would relate to the interview questions adding in further evidence for analysis. Both methods of data collection had pre-determined audiences and populations for target data collection.

4.2. INTERVIEWEES (N=15)

In orchestrating the interviews, I intentionally sought to interview a sample population that included academics, current cohort master's students, and persons within my cruise organisation. I chose this audience in relation to the following:

- **Academics:** In hopes to provide a higher level, educational review of the model from trusted and known sources in the practice of higher education and academia.
- **Current Cohort Master's Students:** The goal would be to seek an ontological perspective of someone that has been on the same academic level journey that I have been involved with. A reflection from my peers.
- **Cruise Organisation:** To include members of my organisation to enquire if the model I have created could have an impact on the very teams that I work with in order to progress sales transformation and lead them through change.

With the intentional design of the types of people that I wanted to interview, I then sought out to identify who they would be. Knowing that I would be under a time constraint and also working in the middle of a global pandemic, as well as having to relocate from my

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home in Barcelona to Miami, I carefully selected people out of these three areas that I felt I could potentially secure the interviews (See Appendix K).

After identifying who my audience would be, I reached out and began the scheduling of interviews both during and after my relocation between Barcelona and Miami that occurred on July 24th. I was truly fortunate to be set up in a corporate apartment in Miami that had all the comforts of home and most importantly the internet, already set up. As we continue to live in the era of a global medical pandemic, the offices are closed, and we are forced to work from home. In my relocation to the USA, I was entering an environment where over 40 million people (Times 2020), (See Figure 4B), would have just lost their jobs. One could safely conclude that many people were in fact, SCARED. We were truly are living in unprecedented times.

Our global cruise business was halted in early May of 2020 and we are still in the process of getting all our crew back to their perspective countries. The workload was quite unpredictable and uncertain since we were dependent for the first time in history, on the Centers for Disease Control (CDC) in the United States to confirm whether we could sail or not. As of this time in my research, our ships were put on a “No Sail”⁵ order by the CDC until the end of September 2020. (Coronavirus Disease 2019: July 16, 2020 Press Release, 2020). Our focus is and was on the health and safety of our crew, our employees, and our guests and as such, the work routine is far from typical. I had annotated this into this research write up as a way of documenting the times and history of this moment as it adds to the level of complexity in not only participating in this research, but also engaging others to participate in this research. At this moment in time, people were **scared**, and they were asking **so what**

⁵ No Sail is an order from the CDC stating that no vessel may sail from a US port with ticketed passengers. All crew except for necessary to the health and safety of the vessel must be repatriated to their homes.

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can they do about being in this type of a change situation. For a research work-based project to uncover the usefulness of a change model of this type, the timing, while unprecedented, was opportune.

The interviews were conducted in a virtual setting, at home due to the global pandemic and the need for mass self-quarantine. We were not permitted to conduct in-person interviews due to health restrictions and extreme caution. I reached out to my audience via email and in some cases via web or phone calls. My audience was eager and willing to participate and as such, I scheduled the virtual sessions in times that would suit both of our calendars and working schedules.

In my initial correspondence I attached my official consent letter and participant information sheet (See Appendix L). I numbered the consent letters in sequential numbers as to be able to remove any names when it comes time to analyze the data (See Appendix K). I created a power point shell presentation (See Appendix M) that would serve as my guidance to facilitate the virtual session. It included my open-ended questions to ensure that I captured the interviewee’s perceptions, feelings, and suggestions and recommendations for the personal change model. I always asked for their permission prior to recording the interviews and would not proceed until I had their permission. I would then re-read that I had their consent and permission to record the interview as evidence during the recorded session with their “yes” response on record.

The use of the visual aid allowed for an easy semi-structured approach that was neither rushed, nor lax in timing and permitted the interviewee ample time to answer each open question. I used Microsoft Teams (See Appendix N) to record the video sessions along with Zoom meetings and both allowed for me to obtain documented transcriptions of the entire conversations to be used for evidence and data analysis later. Between August 26th to September 23rd, I had conducted fifteen, thirty-minute interview sessions. Some went longer as the interviewee would have more to contribute, but the majority were conducted within the thirty-minute time frame.

While my relocation process went much smoother and faster than I had anticipated, I also reflected on advice from Dr. Christine Eastman, in that I should also be not afraid to reach out to known authors and academics from our previous reading requirements in the

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master’s program. As a result, in deep reflection on what was my source in creation of the SCARED-SO WHAT™ personal change model, I decided to reach out to Ken Ross, the son of Dr. Elisabeth Kubler Ross.

Dr. Ross created the Kübler-Ross Change Curve that has been converted by unknown sources into the SARA Curve. I was conflicted from the first day in class that I learned about it. My gut was telling me that the SARA Curve might not truly be the Kübler-Ross Change Curve and that she did not intend for it to turn out this way. Since Dr. Kübler-Ross is no longer with us, reaching out to her son Ken, the President of the Kübler-Ross Foundation, just made sense to me. He continues to champion her research today in partnership with a board of academics and global research leaders. It was much to my surprise and honor that he immediately replied and agreed to participate in my research interviews (See Appendix N).

As part of my research I wanted to include other academics from our Master’s teachings: John Kotter, author of Accelerate, Daryl Connor creator of the Positive Change Curve, Simen Sinek, author and public lecturer on “Why”, Jim Kouzes and Bryan Posner who authored The Leadership Challenge, David Wilkinson, Professor of the Oxford Review and author of Ambiguity Advantage, David Kessler, Author on Grief and academic partner to Dr. Kübler-Ross, and finally to Susan Bridges, President of William Bridges, in where her late husband created of the Bridges Transition model.

Daryl Conner responded but was in the process of launching a new academic program and was not able to participate. I was sincerely honored that he took the time to respond in several emails (See Appendix O). I had received communication from Kotter’s representatives as well with interest but was not able to secure an interview in time (See Appendix P). Likewise, the same result from Kouzes and Posner’s representatives (See Appendix Q).

4.3. SURVEYS

I decided that my audience for the survey portion would need to be a bit expanded due to the current global pandemic. My concern was that the world was caught up in mass confusion and disruptive change, and that participation in my online surveys might not be

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considered necessary by the potential participants. That being said, I thought that the personal change model was quite appropriate to help people in navigating their personal fears and that SCARED-SO WHAT™ might have the ability to help others in this very real-world crisis. As such, my intended audience for the online surveys consists of four main areas:

- **Pilot Group:** A mix of 10 internal current and former employees that I utilized SCARED-SO WHAT™ with during my transition while in Barcelona. These people were already familiar with the model and I wanted to see if the web site delivery helped to solidify their understanding and usability.
- **Main Group:** This includes 170 internal current employees from Royal Caribbean International, Celebrity Cruises, and Azamara Cruises from Europe, Middle East, Africa, Singapore, Australia & New Zealand, to USA and Latin America and Caribbean. These people were already exposed to the model that was included into a new sales training course called “Selling Beyond Covid-19” that I built during the master’s program. This audience was already using the model to help them through the change exposed from the global pandemic. I wanted their feedback after having experienced using it.
- **Facebook Group:** I wanted to try and gain outside perspectives from people that had never heard of the personal change model and as such, I would post to my internal connections and the public.
- **LinkedIn Group:** I wanted to try and gain outside perspectives from business, peers, colleagues, and the open professional community through a professional online setting. I would post to my internal connections and the public.

For the Pilot Group, I first obtained permission from the three main cruise brand leaders to conduct the online surveys within my organisation (See Appendix R). I conducted the Pilot Group surveys from September 5th and leaving them open until September 30th. This group was rather easy and within a week, I had 9 out of 10 responses.

I built the Qualtrics surveys via the Middlesex University platform into the four separate and individually identifiable data sets. The surveys would not collect any identifiable information that I could relate back to trace to the participants (See Appendix S).

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At the same time as the pilot group, I posted the Facebook and LinkedIn group surveys with their own individual Qualtrics links and will close them down on the 30th as well. These surveys were perplexing in the fact that by simply posting online with graphics and word formats, the participation never took off after one week. No-one had responded nor participated in the surveys. I had several likes and one or two shares, but it just was not having the action I had anticipated. "Could this be due to the global pandemic?" I wondered. I asked that same question to my husband of whom does his business online and he instructed that I should try a video to entice engagement in the social media platforms. This is the practice of action learning (McNiff 2017) where you reflect on your learnings during your process and take action as you work.

I built out a web page with GoDaddy.com (See Appendix T) for the new SCARED-SO WHAT™ model from June to July 15th, 2020 as a way for me to visually share the model with internal employees.

I then created videos to advertise the ability to participate in the Qualtrics survey online via a Scared So What Facebook and Instagram page to reference the Facebook Group. Likewise, I did the same for the LinkedIn group and posted videos inviting participation there (See Appendix U).

As it turns out, videos worked much better than static posts. And as a result, at the time, I had received 15 participants between posting the videos on Facebook, Instagram and on LinkedIn. This told me that social media needs to have actions to capture participation and or interest.

For the Main Group, I conducted the surveys from September 13th and closed on September 30th. I must admit that we were already experiencing survey fatigue at our organisation. We had been sending out an abundance of surveys to the tune of 15 to 20 over the past few months. And as a result, I did not anticipate the participation rate to be above 10% of the 170 people invited. However, I was pleased to report, I already had 23 responses and at the time, was just over 13% response rate (See Appendix V).

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4.4 REFLECTION ON ACTIONS TAKEN

My research took place during one of the most ever-changing critical moments in my lifetime thus far. We were and still are amid a global health crisis and pandemic that has as of September 25th, 2020, had infected over 32 million and killed just under 1 million people (University, 2020), (See Appendix W).

While I had not begun the data analysis process, I could already conclude from the interviews alone, that many of my interview participants were living in a time that has left them scared. The Covid-19 pandemic was the main discussion topic when using or referencing the SCARED-SO WHAT™ model, in my interviews. I can attest that this group of individuals were looking for what it is they can do to get through this extraordinary time.

I had found myself through these interviews each time in a better position to handle the stresses that were coming to me and happening with my interviewees as well. One of my key learnings was that many were using this Covid-19 global pandemic as their personal change scenario that they were assessing themselves on and with the models. As such, with each passing interview, I was feeling a little bit better and more positive that it was helping them to navigate their feelings and more importantly, helping to develop their own SO WHAT.

Another key learning was that as I came away from each interview, I also found that the SCARED-SO WHAT™ model was easy to use as a coaching tool with others in my everyday work. I did not expect that. But as many interviewees had confirmed, this model is very agreeable to real life, current situation, coaching scenarios. As they had claimed, I too was finding it useful to guide open ended questions with others. I was beginning to believe there may be another useful purpose for the model through coaching.

This masters research process and my journey with the masters in leading transformative change, and the discovery and use of my new personal change model, were truly what was helping me to get through this global crisis. It felt as if it was meant to be and that I was supposed to be here and go through this situation to help not only myself, but the greater we. The model has now been exposed to literally thousands of people within my organisation and externally throughout our travel partners around the world across language,

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culture, and generations. I felt and still do feel this is only the beginning for SCARED-SO WHAT™ and for me on this journey.

And on a special note, during my data collection processing time, my personal change model SCARED-SO WHAT™ was since been published in the *International Journal of Sales Transformation* (Van Ulbrich, 2020), as well as *The Change Management Review* (Van Ulbrich, 2020). It was also publicly launched on *RCL Cares – Selling Beyond Covid-19*, as a part of Royal Caribbean Group’s global sales training online course for the travel agent community (Van Ulbrich, 2020), (See Appendix X).

CHAPTER 5: DATA ANALYSIS

5.1. LAYING THE GROUNDWORK

The aims I have pursued in this project as an insider researcher were to ascertain if my new personal change model would be useable by others in supporting their own ability to understand and navigate a personal change scenario. In doing so, my main objectives and their actions during this work-based project were as follows:

- Package the model into a user-friendly digestible presentation.
- Engage my employee base in reviewing, ascertaining usefulness and gaining feedback.
- Introduce externally to my travel partner base located in Europe, Middle East, and Africa for usefulness and feedback.
- Get the model published in a professional journal.

My final objective was to collect data through “...mixed methods consisting of combinations of qualitative and quantitative approaches”, known as a mixed-method approach (Flick 2018). My aim through this final objective was to assess feasibility and usefulness of the model as a mechanism to support the individual’s own navigation of personal change. My analysis is based on 15 documented and transcribed interviews and 43 Qualtrics survey responses. In this next chapter, I will identify how I analyzed the data and what approach I used in reviewing the data.

5.2. DEDUCTIVE APPROACH WITH THEMATIC ANALYSIS IN SUPPORT OF RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Planning for my analysis of the variable data subsets, I decided that I would take a deductive approach (Elo and Kyngäs, 2008) with a thematic analysis (Flick 2018) viewpoint. A deductive approach incorporates prior theories or models and I have had prior theories throughout using the SCARED-SO WHAT™ personal change model both from within my organization as well as externally as to its feasibility and usefulness. Thematic analysis “Involves the search across a data set...to find repeated patterns of meaning.” (Braun &

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Clarke, 2006, p. 86, Flick 2018, p. 474). The Thematic Analysis is conducted through six steps as identified in figure 5A.

Figure 5A: Steps of Thematic Analysis (Flick, 2018 pp. 475)

1. FAMILIARIZING YOURSELF WITH YOUR DATA
2. GENERATING INITIAL CODES
3. SEARCHING FOR THEMES
4. REVIEWING THEMES
5. DEFINING AND NAMING THEMES
6. PRODUCING THE REPORT (BROWN AND CLARKE 2006, PP. 87-93)

In following this approach, I found myself literally reading and re-reading the interviews through their transcribed form (See Appendix Z). All the while, my focus was to find answers in support of my research questions. To remind yourself of my research questions please refer to chapter 2.3 pp13-14.

As a way to pull out any themes to be identified through the data collection, I took the research questions and mapped them out in an Excel worksheet and coded the data from each of the interviewees responses as a first step. (See Figure 5B).

Figure 5B: Medium Structured Interview Outcomes

Medium Structured Interview Outcomes									
Question	SIMPLE		HELPPFUL		USABLE				Interviewee's Voice
ID #	1. How easy is the model to use?	2. Can you still use either what each of the letters mean?	3. HELPPFUL - SCARED	4. HELPPFUL - SO WHAT	5. Would you be able to use this model on your own?	6. How would you use this model?	7. Would you use both parts together: SCARED-SO WHAT?	8. Is one part more usable over the other?	KEY QUOTATION
1000	Understand concept	Indirectly could identify	Helpful - Change is not inevitable	you can't take ownership until you're your authentic self owns it. Excellent for coaching	yes	Taking Ownership is the most important part.	Yes	Both used together - excellent for coaching.	"The model is helpful. Change is not inevitable. Scared-So what puts you in the driver seat so you can question your way through it.", "The Power of Choice is taking ownership over change. Scared-So what helps you do that.", "Scared-So what can give you power over fear of the other?"
1001	Very Good - Easy to understand	Able to identify majority	I really understood what is possible.	This might be something that you could discover in a coaching scenario. This could be beneficial as a coaching tool and not just personal. Excellent for coaching.	Yes, because I've actually used it.	Can be used in personal, coaching or business.	Yes over time	Both used together over time. Helpful for personal and excellent for coaching.	"If you try to do the SO WHAT on it's own, you're not dealing with the emotional aspects of change"
1002	Yes, Very easy to use.	Need a little practice.	I found it really helpful and wouldn't have done this normally. Keep Conflicted and Champion as they relate to both ends of the energy spectrum.	The words SO WHAT are great to ask so what will I do about the change. It follows logic. It is difficult at first but for me would be a "learned" model over time.	Difficult at first without learning how to use it...but then a good tool. I can use it on myself.	Definitely could be used as a coaching tool with learned use.	Yes, the thought process must be connected.	SCARED was more usable for me as it helped me to challenge my thinking about what mindset I am in towards change. And perhaps I was in the wrong mindset.	"The So what is so great because it challenges you to do something about the change.", "It's designed to give you permission to look at your feelings and then asks SO WHAT are you going to do about it?"

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Excel workbook data base. Here in this form, it was simple to plot out charts and graphs relevant to the questions and to provide a quantitative viewpoint in answering the research questions and further clarifying visible themes. (See appendix AC). I was also able to pull out a Net Promoter Score (NPS) which is very heavily used in global business models to show the customers voice in ranking businesses and services offered to consumers. (See appendix AD). Quite surprising, the SCARED-SO WHAT™ model generated an NPS of 39, of which is classified (Bain and Company, 2020) just above the low side of GREAT.

5.3. EMERGING THEMES

At the onset, there are three themes that become clear about the feasibility and potential usefulness of the SCARED-SO WHAT™ personal change model as a tool towards navigating personal change. There was an unexpected fourth theme that revealed itself throughout the data and that involves transformation of the model versus the way I had intended for it to be used. While the data in of itself appears to be strong, I realize that this research study has had a very limited amount of time to be conducted and that I was the sole researcher and reviewer of the data. My uncovering of these themes leans themselves towards potential recommendations, however, I must be respectful to the data to advise that further research still yet needs to be achieved. And with a greater audience of participation into the study, additional outcomes might yet be yielded. That said, the following themes are what I have uncovered from my review and study of the data.

5.3.1. SIMPLISTIC FOR PERSONAL AND PROFESSIONAL USE

Examining the data from the interviews illustrated that the model itself leans toward simplicity for use no matter if the change scenario is personal or professional. Respondents used the model for both personal situations arising from the onset of the global pandemic and issues faced with family members through to scenarios faced with employees and business colleagues around the globe.

When examining the data from the surveys with 43 respondents of whom were almost equal in gender and age diversity, and across at least three or more languages, (See appendix AB) I deduced that 83.8% found the models to be simple to use. I also used the word cloud tool to visually pull out and emphasize if the model was simple. Figure 5C highlights that it was simple with the words Quite Easy, Simple, and Really Easy, at the core. When asked if

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they could identify what the letters SCARED referenced, 88% could identify the meanings of the letters correctly. That same question was asked to all those surveyed about the meaning of the letters in SO WHAT and 84% could identify them correctly. Using word cloud on this data segment further highlights in figure 5C that people described the letters as Identifiable, Correctly, Able, Yes, as words to suggest the tool was memorable and identifiable. And finally, the data revealed that 72% of those surveyed got both the SCARED and the SO WHAT meanings correct together. (See appendix AC).

While that does leave 12% to 16% of those surveyed whom could not identify what the letters actually meant, that part was almost insignificant in the fact that they were able to follow the tools instruction without the need to remember the acronyms. In the interviews conducted, some could identify and remember every letter correctly, and then others could only vaguely remember but said they could follow the instruction of the model and the part that was memorable the most, was the words SCARED – SO WHAT. Respondent 1008 stated "Scared-So What is very clean, focused, easy to digest and makes sense. It's right there in center field."⁶ Overall, the data suggests that the model itself was easy and simple to use – even if just following it letter by letter and not having to commit it to memory. Respondent 1013 sums up this theme perfectly, *"It's a very important model specifically because it can be applied to both personal life and a professional work life as well."*

5.3.2. HELPFULNESS IS RELATIVE TO INDIVIDUAL NEED

"The model is helpful. Change is not inevitable. Scared-So what puts you in the driver seat so you can question your way through it," said respondent 1000. This sets the tone for the general census of those interviewed. The data also leans towards the model being helpful in very personal ways. In some instances, respondents leaned towards the SCARED model while others leaned towards the SO What model. The leaning of one way or the other was dependent upon the emotional state and situation of the individual experiencing the change scenario. But overwhelmingly, the majority of respondents agreed that both models must be used together. Respondent 1001 said, *"If you try to do the SO WHAT on its own, you're not dealing with the emotional aspects of change"*. Alternatively respondent 1004 said, *"The*

⁶ Direct quotations from interviews can be seen in appendix AE. Permission for quotations were obtained and recorded during interviews.

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SCARED part of the model, and the quiz, helped me to clarify my mindset and give me some breathing space to think a little bit about myself... which I don't normally do." These views were expressed in their own individual ways to reflect on their own needs and uses of the models. However, the term “helpful” was always center and relevant in their reflections on using the model.

Alternatively, we can look towards the qualitative data sets to further explain the helpfulness of the models themselves. Of the 43 participants 37.2% expressed that the SCARED model was extremely helpful. Likewise, 46.5% found the SCARED model moderately helpful with another 7% saying it was slightly helpful. Overall, 90.7% defined the SCARED model as a helpful tool.

The SO What model was rated 39.5% as extremely helpful with 37.2% giving it a moderately helpful scoring. And 11.6% found it slightly helpful. Overall, the SO WHAT model was rated at 88.3% helpful as a tool. (See appendix AC).

When looking to the overall helpfulness of the SCARED-SO WHAT™ model, respondent 1014 highlights this, "It's important to know you don't have to be scared to use this model. You can use for whatever type of situation you are in regardless of positive, neutral, or negative and no matter if it's personal or work related."

5.3.3. USEABLE BY ALL WHO PARTICIPATED IN THEIR OWN WAYS

The last of my research questions were shaped to answer the area of usability of the model. When I looked at the interview data with the use of a word cloud, figure 5D highlights that the model was usable by those who participated not only for themselves but for use towards others. The words highlighted reflect “yes, already, can, used”, as to suggest positive usability. And when it comes to the question of together or separate, the consensus is “yes”, you can “use” the two “parts together”. See figure 5D.

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It would be through an interview I held with Dr. Kübler-Ross’s son, Ken Ross⁷, President of his mother’s foundation (See appendix AF), were I would learn the true answer if she had in fact created the SARA Curve or not. And the answer was that she did not create the SARA Curve version we see today used in everyday business settings and in this very master’s course training. She was aware, later in her life, of people wanting to use and reference it towards business. There were in fact 10 stages in her research and at one time up to 13. Her stages were not linear nor prescribed to be fitting to each person experiencing oncoming death or loss. She just wanted to be able to facilitate a conversation on death and dying. Nowhere did she intend for it to be used in business. That said, models do change through the eyes of others. Like Dr. Kübler-Ross, I too, want to facilitate a conversation about personal change, and am open to my model possibly having other uses.

During my interview process, I found that like Dr. Kübler-Ross’s model, where people were ready and willing to find another use for her model, people were already finding another use for the SCARED-SO WHAT™ model. A transformation was already in the making even if I have only just now begun to share the model with the world. Respondent 1018 said, *"As a practitioner, I think it's a great model to look change in the lens of the way they may be feeling. It can also be a great coaching tool."* Respondent 1003 said, *"As a coaching tool, it gives you a way forward - which is what coaching is all about."* It kept coming up that the personal change model could be used as a coaching tool. I listened and wanted to take action to expand this into my inquiry.

Therefore, in my online surveys, I included one question on that subject to see how others would feel about the usability of the personal change model as a coaching tool. Of the 43 respondents, 51% strongly agreed, 23% agreed, while 14% agreed somewhat. That gave an overall favorability of approximately 88% suggesting that SCARED-SO WHAT™ might have another use other than what I had originally intended, and that use would be towards coaching. (See appendix AC).

⁷ Permission to record and disclose Ken Ross’s interview data into this project was received during the interview.

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5.4. A REMINDER ABOUT ETHICS AND IMPORTANCE OF UNCONSCIOUS BIAS

“Perhaps it is only in the areas of ethical consideration that the IARr may not have an advantage vis-a`-vis an outside consultant,” (Ranjan Kumar 2013). An outside consultant would be able to view the data and have an unbiased opinion on the results. However, as an IARr, it would have been quite easy for me to surmise that this data all represents favorability of my own creation. However, that would be not only representative of self-bias, but also, unethical.

What I can surmise from this experience is that there was a tight timeline on the project to be conducted by myself as the insider researcher within my organisation and that I was the only person to be able to review this data as in-depth as a part of this write up. It is my hope that by having laid out my foundation, methodology, and methods taken, in the undertaking of this research, that perhaps another independent researcher may also come to the same conclusion and deduction.

The data as evidence leans towards a favorable outcome in answering the three main research questions. However, I know that further research with greater participant reach and other independent data reviewers would be warranted to further support and strengthen my claim. For that, I would welcome peer reviewers and researcher feedback.

5.5. CONCLUSION ON DATA ANALYSIS

At the onset of taking on this project, I hypothesized that this model could have potential value in supporting others in navigating their own way through personal change. And since its creation, I have come to use and embed the model into my own way of critical thinking about change. It is during this master’s program that I too, have experienced an abundance of change, from taking the masters course itself, to closing my organizations office locations in Europe and relocating back to our Miami headquarters in just the past few months. And all the while, maintaining my role within our organisation even through countless layoffs, furloughs, and the complete shutdown of our industry due to the global pandemic. For this alone, the value of creating this model and conducting this research, if only for myself, has proven beneficial and changed my way of thinking about navigating personal change.

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I am confident that the way I conducted this research, and the analysis of the data subsets would be replicable by other researchers. That said, I am confident that with the way I have analyzed the data, other reviewers might be able to verify the outcomes for themselves. The data leans towards the SCARED-SO WHAT™ personal change model as being favorable in the areas of simplicity, helpfulness, and usability. But it also suggests that it is up to the individual to assess the answers to each of those questions for themselves. Not every person will use the model in the same methods, and that is ok.

It would have been very beneficial if given more time to analyze the data, I would have been able to conduct Participative Action Research and share the data outcomes and review in a group sitting and or social format to invite further scrutiny and discussion of potential outcomes. However, it was not possible to do this type of research during the timeframe and setting. That said, I am pleased with my review of the project and the data analysis as it stands. In this next chapter, I will start to provide my recommendations towards further study and use of the SCARED-SO WHAT™ personal change model.

CHAPTER 6: KEY FINDINGS, RECOMMENDATIONS, CRITICAL REFLECTION & CONCLUSION

6.1. KEY FINDINGS

My aims and objectives in creating a new personal change model that I’ve called SCARED-SO WHAT, were to challenge my own perspectives and bias of the model to discover if it would be simple, helpful and useful in navigating personal change. In that, below I have written my key findings to my aims and objectives I set out to achieve in this research.

- Package the model into a user-friendly digestible presentation. I achieved this by creating the model on an open public website at www.scaredsowhat.com free for all to use and consume.
- Engage my employee base in reviewing, ascertaining usefulness and gaining feedback. This was achieved through both qualitative interviews and quantitative survey data measures. The model was also delivered to internal sales members across the globe through a course called “Selling Beyond Covid-19” (Van Ulbrich, 2020) and had a reach of over 170 employees.
- Introduce externally to my travel partner base located in Europe, Middle East, and Africa for usefulness and feedback. This was achieved by creating a new online sales training course in RCL Cares⁸ (Van Ulbrich, 2020), for all in the general travel public to consume. A snapshot of data shows that 1,148 travel partners actively engaged in consuming the course that includes the SCARED-SO WHAT™ model. (See appendix Y)
- Get the model published in a professional journal. This was achieved through the International Journal of Sales Transformation and The Change Management Review, among other travel related publication references as stated in chapter 4. (See appendix X).

⁸ RCL Cares is a travel agency training and reference site located at www.rclcares.co.uk and is accessible throughout Europe, Middle East, and Africa. It is produced by Royal Caribbean Group with contributing authors for content in support of the global pandemic and the cessation of cruise travel.

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My aim through my final objective was to assess feasibility and usefulness of the model as a mechanism to support the individual’s own navigation of personal change. In this next section, I will share my recommendations on my findings from my research.

6.2. RECOMMENDATIONS

It is important for me to recognize that as the creator of this new personal change model, there may be criticism by others in the change management community as well as individual change leaders from across organizations and individual inputs and concerns on the outcomes and my recommendations from this research. I do realize and am aware of my own bias towards the effectiveness of the new personal change model. That said, I suggest and hope that the research on the model will continue and that others may construct their own opinions. I welcome other contributions and much like Dr. Elisabeth Kübler-Ross, I only want to facilitate a discussion and I believe this model can do just that.

The data that I have researched and analyzed leads me to make the following recommendations knowing that they can only be strengthened with further research and collection of opinions.

1. **SIMPLICITY:** The new personal change model SCARED-SO WHAT™ presents as a simple tool to use for adults age 26 years and upwards, after careful absorption in following the model as represented on the website at www.scaredsowhat.com. Participants interviewed and surveyed (See chapter 5.3.1. on pp 40-41) found the tool easy, simple, and digestible in understanding its meaning and purpose in both English and Spanish as well as other languages in sampling from around the globe.
2. **HELPFULNESS:** The new personal change model SCARED-SO WHAT™ lends itself as a tool (See chapter 5.3.2. pp 41-42) that is helpful for individual use in navigating personal or professional change regardless if positive, negative, or neutral. The term helpful must be noted that it is helpful in an individualistic way. Helpfulness is in of itself to be determined individually. The model can be used either together or separately, but almost all participants recommend it is more helpful when used together (See figure 5D p 43). The consensus is that

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SCARED helps in navigating feelings towards a change scenario, while the SO WHAT portion helps in developing individual action plans to enact, execute, or deal with a change scenario.

3. **USEABLE:** My evidence (See chapter 5.3.3. pp 42-43) suggests that the new personal change model SCARED-SO WHAT™ has presented itself to be a useable tool in navigating personal or professional change. How one chooses to use the model is based on individual needs, understanding of the change being imposed on or with them. However, each participant strongly favors using both the SCARED and the SO WHAT portions together to achieve maximum usability. Respondent 1014 summed up most responses with *"It's important to know you don't have to be scared to use this model. You can use for whatever type of situation you are in regardless of positive, neutral, or negative and no matter if it's personal or work related."* And respondent 1001 said this important note that was shared by most *"If you try to do the SO WHAT on its own, you're not dealing with the emotional aspects of change."*
4. **A TOOL FOR COACHING:** While it was not my intent to create a tool for coaching, the overwhelming response by the participants (See chapter 5.3.4. pp 43-44) suggests that the personal change model SCARED-SO WHAT™ has the potential to be used as a tool in coaching others. This came up in many interview responses and as a result, was asked to all in the surveys with an 88% favorable response towards using as a coaching tool. And another 7% had neutrality towards using it as a coaching tool. While I do have some suggestions from participants on how to use it, further research needs to be conducted on feasibility and how the model would perform as a coaching tool. Therefore, it is too early for me to recommend this now without further research being conducted.

6.3. CRITICAL REFLECTION

In October of 2018, I set out on this new journey in participating in the world's first master's program exclusively dedicated towards sales transformation. As a sales leader for a global organization, it is my duty and responsibility to continue championing my own

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professional development in the hopes that I can help others to grow and thus transform. That said, I had no idea of how active I would be at the center of my own transformation.

I thought that I would gain new tips of information, new ideas, and maybe broaden out some of the existing knowledge that I had already obtained throughout my sales career. That could not have been further from the truth about what I was about to experience and how I would completely transform my own thinking about selling and sales and what it means to transform. I thought that transformation was impacting on others, but true transformation begins with me.

This journey has been a difficult one not only just for the time limitations, learning new academic language, taking on the project research and work that comes with the master’s program, but also continuing to manage my day-to-day role and merging my new learning directly into my work practice. That in of itself, has been a huge transformation in the way I conduct my sales craft. I now have a new sense of how to research, how to perform inquiry as an insider researcher, and how to lead not only for myself, but for leading others in a more evidence-based practice. The master’s program has transformed the way I work from prior sales theoretical point of view, towards sales evidence and fact-based decision making.

The focal point of my research project came during the program on module four when we learned about change and how to lead change. It was there, where I challenged the intent and use of existing change models and I concluded that they were mostly leaning towards organisational change and not individual change. That did not sit well with me and as I challenged the models, my professor challenged me to create something different. And that is what I did.

6.4. CONCLUSION

I am very thankful for this opportunity to conduct this research. It has truly transformed my own thinking as a leader in sales. While the project itself focuses on the creation of a new personal change model, for me, it 100% applies towards leading sales transformation. My career in sales has been trial and error and lessons learned along the way. Until now, sales as a career, in my opinion, has not been professionalized through formal academic curriculum without having a major emphasis on marketing. This is the first

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program I have been through that is exclusively focused on my craft in selling and sales. Change is at the heart of everything we do in sales and I cannot begin to count the times over the years that I have challenged thinking on selling through a change initiative.

My literature review truly uncovered for me my question of “Where are the models that are designed to help me change?” The models we have been subjected to lean toward benefiting organizations and not the individual. Yet, it is the individual, like me, that must execute these changes. The creation of the new personal change model SCARED-SO WHAT™ was created to help others in navigating their own way through personal change – and thus giving them the ability to transform. While the data suggests that it can achieve that goal, I can say that it 100% has transformed me and my own thinking about change.

I am now transformed from whom I used to be before the master’s program. With this new model, I now have the ability to embrace my own personal change and ask myself “Am I SCARED? What feelings am I experiencing? Have I made a favorable decision to embrace this change? And if yes, then SO WHAT will I do about it? The tool has become more of a way of thinking for me to use in the moment. I do not have to read it, pull it out and write it down. After using it so much during this project, it has become a way of thinking about change. So, the best outcome for this is that while I do believe and the data suggests that it can help others, it has helped me to embrace change and become a better leader and a better person to myself and others around me. And for that I claim it to be successful and worthwhile in creating if not only for others...but for me.

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Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT

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Including ‘Choice’ into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT

APPENDICES:

Appendix A: OVERVIEW OF THE SCARED-SO WHAT™ MODEL

An overview of the **SCARED-SO WHAT™** change model.

SCARED-SO WHAT™ is a new change model that is designed to incorporate positive, neutral, or negative, change experiences that a person may find themselves involved within a certain situation. The change may be self-imposed or thrust upon them with or without notice.

The model is designed to help a person to stop and ask themselves “Where am I within this change process?” That is what the SCARED model is designed to help with.

The SO WHAT part of the model is the next stage to help the person involved in the change to formulate their own “So What” can they do about the change.

“Change is personal, and change is constant – how you navigate the change makes it bearable and achievable.”

Grant Van Ulbrich, creator of the **SCARED-SO WHAT™** change methodology.

Figure 1: SCARED model

Looking at the first part (in Figure 1), SCARED is a non-linear model that can resemble change in real life, at work or at home moments, where people identify with fear. Remember, while the fear of change is called *Metathesiophobia*, you do not have to take the model literally. You do not have to be “Scared” for the model to work. You’ll also notice that over time, people can express neutral, positive, or negative reactions in their behaviour as each element applies to them in the cycle.

Surprise can be positive or negative. People can be **Conflicted** or **Champion** the change. **Actions** will occur when people begin to ask questions or seek clarity of the change. People can become **Receptive** or flat out **Reject** the change being imposed upon them. Next, one might **Explore** options or a way forward before coming to a **Decision** point.

In the SCARED model, during a change process, the goal is to break out of the fear of change with a favourable decision point. If one cannot, then they may repress themselves back into the SCARED cycle until they can. If they remain inside this cycle it could be due to indecision or absence of information. SCARED identifies the behaviours and moods that one might experience during an at-work change management process.

Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT

APPENDIX A: OVERVIEW OF THE SCARED-SO WHAT™ MODEL - CONTINUED

An example of the SCARED model over time (in Figure 2), and energy is represented here. Note that the stages will move up and down depending on the persons experience. The process is not linear, and one may skip or bypass a portion of the cycle. The experience and results will be personal to the individual going through the change process.

Figure 2: SCARED over time & energy

Figure 3: SO WHAT

In the SO WHAT model (as seen here in Figure 3), **Strategy** may be the first step to begin with. And to add to your strategy you may need **Options** or opportunities to enhance that change management strategy. Once you have your strategy and options, you quickly assess if this is the proper **Way forward** for you.

If not, then go back and rework your plan.

If yes, then you stop and do a sense check to see if you have **Hope** or know fully **How** you can move forward. Once you are sure of your plan then you need to take the **Actions** necessary to enable your plan. **Taking ownership** will ensure that your plan succeeds. This is

detailed further in the **SO WHAT** templates to help one complete their **SO WHAT** plan. The combined models for a simple personal change-management process comes together as **SCARED – SO WHAT™**.

Including ‘Choice’ into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT

APPENDIX A: OVERVIEW OF THE SCARED-SO WHAT™ MODEL - CONTINUED

The SO WHAT template below can help you as a guide to formulate your own SO WHAT. Use this to prompt your thinking in making your own plan.

STRATEGY:

- Identifying and clarifying the change
- Steps to include in the change
- Processes and People that need to be involved in the change – Who needs to be involved
- Needs / constraints / support mechanisms / budgets / tools
- Timelines

OPTIONS:

- Identifying other options and opportunities – Socialize the plan and gain support
- People and processes necessary to support the plan – fact check, and sense check the plan
- Workshops may be necessary (Small or Large) for Idea generation / collaboration
- Support needed / processes and people

WAY FORWARD:

- Identifying who will need to be in the Review / Approval process
- Identifying stakeholders – Blockers / Supporters
- Workshops or support needed

HOPE/HOW:

- Do I have the right plan in place?
- Do I have the teams buy in and support or are they still stuck in the SCARED model?
- Do I have the leadership support / approval of my Strategic plan and Way Forward?
- Note: I may need to revisit the Strategy, Options and recalculate my Way Forward.
- If I'm ok with the above, then I can move forward.

ACTIONS:

- What actions do you need to take?
- Who do you need to help take this plan forward now that it's approved and ready?
- Begin your plan to include:
 - Leadership support launch, Communication process, Implementation process
 - Key Performance Measures, Timelines

TAKE OWNERSHIP:

- Holding myself accountable
- Sharing and communicating your vision
- Checking and supporting the implementation leaders
- Reporting out progress and continued support of those involved
- Checking in with people involved to ensure they have what is necessary (Might be with yourself)
- Seeing your plan through and asking for help when necessary
- Celebrate success / and or Regroup if necessary to bring people back into supporting for success

Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT

APPENDIX B: WHAT I WILL SEARCH FOR.

What medium will I use?	What words will I search for?	What category is it?	Why?	Is there a date range?	What did I find?	Comments or specific notes?
Medium	Key Words and Phrases	Category	Justification?	Time Frame	Results	Notes
Middlesex University Library Online	"Change Management Models", "Change Models", "Models for Change", "Review of Change Models"	Change Models	Focus is on specific models that a person can use on themselves for understanding and acting on individual change.	1985-2020	"Change Management Models" brought 273 results and found 1 comparative review that focused on change models themselves. "Change Models" brought 16,336 results and after skimming through the first 50 pages, I could not find anything relative to a model review or critique. The masses were on climate change, health change, and theory. "Models for Change" brought 149 results and after skimming through the first 50 pages, I could not find anything relative to a model review or critique. The masses were varied from healthcare to energy, to climate change. "Review of Change Models" brought 1 result which was an Organizational change models and digital library project review. Had nothing to reflect on actual change models.	The one result that I found was actually good review of change management models and is applicable to my literature review in critique of the models themselves. It is titled: Change Management Models: A Comparative Analysis and Concerns by Brian Joseph Galli (2018) Vol.46(3), pp. 124-132 - Peer Reviewed from the Engineering Management Review journal. NOTE: I was also supplied another source by my cohort leader called "Organizational Change Management: A Critical Review" an article in the Journal of Change Management 12/2005 by Rune Todnem for consideration.
Google Scholar - Searched here and then went to Middlesex University Library online to avoid paying for any relevant articles or sources.	"Change Management Models", "Change Models", "Models for Change", "Review of Change Models"	Change Models	Focus is on specific models that a person can use on themselves for understanding and acting on individual change.	1985-2020	"Change Management Models" brought 2,350 results and found 2 items. One interesting doctoral thesis, one comparative analysis, and many that were not relevant as they related to changing organizations themselves. "Change Models" brought 35,500 results and after skimming through the first 50 pages, I could not find anything relative to a model review or critique. The masses were on structures, mathematics, land surface, environmental and various organizational change. "Models for Change" brought 7,110 results and after skimming through the first 50 pages, I could not find anything relative to a model review or critique. The masses were varied from logistics, transition, technology, education and healthcare change. "Review of Change Models" brought 32 results which brought together doctoral thesis papers and studies from general change management, business change, leader behavior inventory, digital and educational change but not the review of change models I was looking to find.	Confirmed the 1 Peer Reviewed comparative analysis that was found on Middlesex University and able to download. NOTE: Then did a general Google Search on "Change Models" to see what would come. The first item was a critical comparison and review of the 8 major change models by a researcher from Process Street: Process Street is a cloud-based business process management (BPM) solution that enables organizations to create checklists and process documents for recurring projects. - Users can manage multiple projects, review ongoing projects, assign tasks and collaborate with team members. The review caught my attention as it was a comprehensive overview of the main change models themselves with the Good and Bad annotations to them. The assessment matched up significantly to the PEEPR REVIEWED critique from Brian Joseph Galli. For this reason, I have decided to include this into my literature review. See search result to the right.

APPENDIX C: WHAT I WILL NOT SEARCH FOR.

What medium will I use?	What won't I search for?	What category is it?	Why?	Is there a date range?	What did I find?	Comments or specific notes?
Medium	Key Words and Phrases	Category	Justification?	Time Frame	Results	Notes
Middlesex University Library Online	"Organizational Change", "Corporate Change", "Change Management", "Leading Change"	General Change - Looking for individual models	Not focusing on organizations, corporations, companies, or overall change structure tools to implement change.	1985-2020	NOT SEARCHING ON THESE	NOT SEARCHING ON THESE
Google Scholar	"Organizational Change", "Corporate Change", "Change Management", "Leading Change"	General Change - Looking for individual models	Not focusing on organizations, corporations, companies, or overall change structure tools to implement change.	1985-2020	NOT SEARCHING ON THESE	NOT SEARCHING ON THESE

APPENDIX D: KURT LEWIN'S CHANGE THEORY.

Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT

APPENDIX E: KOTTER'S EIGHT STAGE CHANGE MODEL.

APPENDIX F: ADKAR CHANGE MODEL.

APPENDIX G: MCKINSEY'S 7-S CHANGE MODEL.

McKinsey's 7-S model for change

Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT

APPENDIX H: ELISABETH KUBLER-ROSS CHANGE CURVE.

Figure 4: Change Curve

APPENDIX I: THE SARA CURVE (ADAPTED FROM ELISABETH KÜBLER-ROSS).

Figure 5: SARA Curve

Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT

APPENDIX J: CONNER'S POSITIVE CHANGE CURVE.

Figure 2: Conner's Positive Change Curve

APPENDIX K: AUDIENCE FOR INTERVIEWS AND DATA TRACKING WORKBOOK

Masters program: MSC Leading Sales Transformation		Supervisor: Chris Rigby		WBS4760		Middlesex University				
Student: Grant Van Ulbrich		Student #: M00701855								
Interviewee Name	ID #	Position	Email	Consent/PIS shared (Y/N)	Date Shared	Consent/PIS obtained (Y/N)	Follow up communication	Interview held on:	TRANSCRIPT	Internal employee, Former employee, External
	1000	Academic		yes	8/24/2020	yes		9/2/2020	YES	external
	1001	Academic		yes	8/24/2020	yes		8/26/2020	YES	external
	1002	Academic		yes	8/24/2020	yes		8/27/2020	YES	external
	1003	Masters Cohort		yes	8/29/2020	yes		9/16/2020	YES	external
	1004	Masters Cohort		yes	8/29/2020	yes		9/16/2020	YES	external
	1005	Cruise Colleague		yes	8/29/2020	yes	9/8/2020	9/13/2020	YES	former employee
	1006	Cruise Colleague		yes	8/29/2020	yes		9/10/2020	YES	employee
	1007	Masters Cohort		yes	8/29/2020	yes		9/23/2020	YES	external
	1008	Academic		yes	8/29/2020	yes		9/9/2020	YES	external
	1009	Academic		yes	8/29/2020		9/8/2020			external
	1010	Cruise Colleague		yes	8/29/2020	yes	9/8/2020	9/22/2020	YES	employee
	1011	Cruise Colleague		yes	8/29/2020	yes		9/9/2020	YES	employee
	1011	Academic		yes	8/29/2020		9/9/2020	No Response		external
	1012	Academic		yes	8/29/2020		9/9/2020	DECLINED		external
	1014	Cruise Colleague		yes	8/29/2020	yes	9/8/2020	9/17/2020	YES	external
	1015	Cruise Colleague		yes	8/29/2020	yes		9/18/2020	YES	employee
	1016	Cruise Colleague		yes	8/29/2020	yes		9/8/2020	YES	employee
	1017	Cruise Colleague		yes	8/29/2020		9/8/2020	No Response		employee

Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT

APPENDIX L: PARTICIPANT INFORMATION AND CONSENT FORMS.

MIDDLESEX UNIVERSITY

Participant Information Sheet (PIS)
More Than Minimal Risk or High Risk Projects
 (Must be used with a Consent Form that is signed by participant and retained by the researcher) June 21, 2020

Participant ID Code: 1004

SECTION 1

1. Project/Study title
 Masters Module 7 Project: WBS4760: Title: "Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SOWHAT: How do I explain change in a modern, simplistic, self-help model that incorporates personal choice and a support mechanism to see the change through?"

2. Invitation paragraph
 You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you do, you need to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. You will be asked to take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with your travel partner. Ask us if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

Thank you for reading this.

3. What is the purpose of the study?
 My aim is to give the SCARED-SO WHAT™ model to people by employees and to others externally for test and review. As Graban states, "The more you give, the more you want to do it – as do others and also states, "People support what they create." (Graban and Swain) key ingredients as I will want to give the models to others thus allow the creation and evolution of the SCARED-SO WHAT™ model.

My main objectives in doing this will be to achieve the following:

- Package the model into a user-friendly digestible presentation
- Engage my employee base in reviewing, usefulness, and feedback
- Introduce externally to my travel partner base for usefulness and feedback
- Get the model published in a professional journal.
- Collect data responses both quantitative and qualitative and usefulness and or to change and adapt the model.

By performing these objectives, I should be in a position to incorporate into my final project dissertation and next steps.

4. Why have I been chosen?
 It is important that we assess as many participants as possible, and that you are interested in taking part in this study. You may be a

Please note: A decision to withdraw at any time, or a decision not to take part, will not affect your status with RCL in any way.

do? Give answers to questions in an interview/questionnaire. No longer than approximately 20 to 30 minutes for interviews.

to ensure quality assurance and equity this project may be assigned a designated member of the committee. This means that the request to see signed consent forms. However, if this is the case, the form will only be accessed by the designated auditor or

ide any bodily samples (i.e. blood/saliva/urine)?

ible disadvantages and risks of taking part? Advantages nor risks in participating in this project. We hope this study will help you. However, this cannot be guaranteed. The data from those sessions to research and frame up the change model accordingly. This research will be used to help further the development of the model structure, subjective, approach. This may result in changing its current format and structure.

ible benefits of taking part? In participating in this project. We hope that participating in this project will help you. However, this cannot be guaranteed. The information we get from those sessions to help round out my change model accordingly. This research project will further the development of the model and follows a socially

Participant Identification Number: 1004

CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SOWHAT
 Name of Researcher: Grant Van Ulbrich

Please initial box

- I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet dated 6.21.2020 for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.
- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw within 3 business days, without giving any reason and without penalty.
- I agree that this form that bears my name and signature may be seen by a designated auditor.
- I agree that my non-identifiable research data may be stored in National Archives and be used anonymously by others for future research. I am assured that the confidentiality of my data will be upheld through the removal of any personal identifiers.
- I understand that my interview may be video recorded and subsequently transcribed.
- I agree to take part in the above study.

Name of participant	Date	Signature
Grant Van Ulbrich Researcher	Aug 24, 2020 Date	

1 copy for participant, 1 copy for researcher

Participant Information Sheet – (PIS) Ver 1.0 More Than Minimal Risk, Middlesex University Ethics (June 21, 2020)

APPENDIX M: INTERVIEW PRESENTATION FOR SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEWS.

Middlesex University
Masters Research Interviews
Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT™

Work Based research masters Project by: Grant Van Ulbrich
 Research Question: How do I explain change in a modern, simplistic, self-help model that incorporates personal choice and a support mechanism to see the change through?
 Researcher: Grant Van Ulbrich
 Research Supervisor: Chris Digby

Preamble
Intro before interview

This is an interview in conducting research towards my work based project on:
 - Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT™
 It is designed to answer the question of:
 - "How do I explain change in a modern, simplistic, self-help model that incorporates personal choice and a support mechanism to see the change through?"

All such, you have agreed to participate and have completed the CONSENT FORM and reviewed the PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET.
 Do I have your permission to record the interview?

Interview
REVIEW OF THE MODEL

Have you had an opportunity to review the SCARED-SO WHAT model on the website at www.scaredsowhat.com?
 If yes, continue.
 If no, stop here.

Interview
HELPFULNESS

Reflecting on the model and your experience using the model, the SCARED Quiz, the SO WHAT template, let's discuss the following questions:

- How easy is the model to use?
- Can you please state what each of the letters mean?

Interview
HELPFULNESS

The next questions look at the model in two parts. The first part is the SCARED section. This portion of the model relates to your views on your personal change scenario of being Positive, Neutral, or a Negative experience.

- Do you feel the SCARED model could help you navigate your feelings (positive or negative), during a change process? If yes, explain how. If no, explain why not?

Interview
HELPFULNESS

The second part is the SO WHAT section. This portion of the model is a template to help guide you in facilitating your own plan of action or support of your personal change scenario.

- Do you feel the SO WHAT model could help you build your own plan to facilitate or execute a change process? If yes, explain how. If no, explain why not?

Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT

APPENDIX N: MICROSOFT TEAMS AND ZOOM VIDEO RECORDED SESSIONS WITH TRANSCRIPTIONS – KEN ROSS EXAMPLE

Home Discover My content Create Search

Interview

The Kübler-Ross Change Curve™

Middlesex University London

The first two questions are in relation to the Kübler-Ross Change Curve™:

1. Do you believe that Dr. Kübler-Ross ever intended for her model to be utilized in main stream everyday business change processes?
2. Do you believe that Dr. Kübler-Ross would have approved of her models being transcribed into the SARA curve today? Shock, Anger, Resistance, Acceptance – as all references give her credit for it's creation.

02:13 / 19:09

Transcript Interactivity

Search transcript

- 02:02 change or loss or anything like that and she said, well of
- 02:06 course it applies to anyone going through any kind of change
- 02:10 or loss. So yes, she knew about it. No, she didn't originally
- 02:15 intend it. Certainly for business he was most anti
- 02:18 business person you've ever met in your life really? Yeah she. I
- 02:23 mean she could not use a

APPENDIX O: CORRESPONDENCE WITH DARYL CONNOR.

All Unread By Date ↑

Last Month

- Daryl Conner
RE: [EXTERNAL] RE: Research Interview Request - Lea... 8/29/2020
- Daryl Conner
[EXTERNAL] RE: Research Interview Request - Leadin... 8/28/2020
- [REDACTED]
[EXTERNAL] RE: Research Interview Request - SCARE... 8/26/2020
- Daryl Conner
Read: [EXTERNAL] Read: Research Interview Request ... 8/25/2020
- [REDACTED]
[EXTERNAL] Re: Research Interview Request - SCARE... 8/25/2020
- Grant Van Ulbrich
Research Interview Request - SCARED-SO WHAT 8/24/2020

RE: [EXTERNAL] RE: Research Interview Reques...

DC Daryl Conner
To Grant Van Ulbrich 8/29/2020

You replied to this message on 8/29/2020 10:19 PM.

EXTERNAL EMAIL CAUTION: Use caution opening attachments or clicking links.

Grant—My decline isn't tied to a review of your model...I'm a bit overwhelmed with client commitments and not able to even dive into what you have formulated. Wish I could be of more help but now is just not the right time for me.

Take care,
Daryl

From: Grant Van Ulbrich <[REDACTED].com>
Sent: Saturday, August 29, 2020 5:32 PM
To: Daryl Conner <[REDACTED]>
Subject: RE: [EXTERNAL] RE: Research Interview Request - Leading Sales Transformation & a new Personal Change Model

Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT

APPENDIX P: CORRESPONDENCE WITH KOTTER'S REPRESENTATIVES.

[EXTERNAL] Connecting with Kotter

 Rod Walker <[redacted]>
To: Grant Van Ulbrich
Mon 6:07 PM

 You replied to this message on 9/21/2020 8:16 PM.
Click here to download pictures. To help protect your privacy, Outlook prevented automatic download of some pictures in this message.

Hello Grant,
I wanted to follow-up with you based on your recent inquiry to Kotter. I would love to setup some time to discuss your research and Sales Transformation at Royal Caribbean Group. Thanks, and I look forward to connecting.

Cheers!
rod w

 ROD WALKER
President
M: 404.227.1020
5 Bennett Street, Cambridge, MA 02138
www.kotterinc.com
Boston | Seattle | London

 Right-click or tap and hold here to download pictures. To help protect your privacy, Outlook prevented automatic download of this picture from the Internet.

APPENDIX Q: CORRESPONDENCE WITH KOUZES & POSNER REPRESENTATIVES.

Re: [EXTERNAL] Interview request

 Sims, Gabriel <[redacted]>
To: Grant Van Ulbrich
Thu 1:52 PM

 You replied to this message on 9/24/2020 2:15 PM.
If there are problems with how this message is displayed, click here to view it in a web browser.

Grant,

Barry and Jim are pretty busy these days. However, Jim may be available for 30 minute conversation.

If you are interested, I will pass his email along to you.

Gabriel Sims

Organizational Psychologist

From: Grant Van Ulbrich <[redacted]>
Sent: Monday, September 21, 2020 2:35:45 PM
To: Sims, Gabriel <[redacted]>
Cc: Barry Posner <[redacted]>; Weinhold, Tricia <[redacted]>
<[redacted]> <[redacted]> <[redacted]>
Subject: RE: [EXTERNAL] Interview request

Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT

APPENDIX R: PERMISSION TO CONDUCT ONLINE SURVEYS.

Re: Your Permission Please - Research

Reply Reply All Forward

Thu 8/27/2020 5:07 PM

You replied to this message on 8/27/2020 5:12 PM.

Hello

I'm writing today to ask your permission to conduct a survey of our teams on the usefulness of the new SCARED-SO WHAT personal change model that I've created as a part of my master's program. www.scaredsowhat.com On the website you can see the new models as well as it has been published now twice.

The SCARED-SO WHAT personal change model was included in the **Selling Beyond Covid-19** course our team members took. And one of my goals is for greater company wide adoption as a resource to support greater success for our change management and sales transformation efforts.

Research has shown that over 70% of change management processes launched, fail. They fail due to the lack of inclusion on the employees own internal needs of understanding and ability to adopt. (*An excerpt from my masters research below supports this finding)

The survey itself will take approximately 10 minutes of their time, with 10 minutes to review the SCARED-SO WHAT model via the website. This is a refresher from the view they've already had in the Selling Beyond Covid-19 course. The survey will not be mandatory, but voluntary and is required for me to collect data in support of my final dissertation of the masters.

May I have your permission to conduct this survey for the international sales teams over the next few weeks?

Thank you very kindly,

Grant

APPENDIX S: QUALTRICS ONLINE SURVEYS.

Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT

APPENDIX T: GO DADDY WEB PAGE WWW.SCAREDSOWHAT.COM

APPENDIX U: VIDEO AND BLOG POSTS ON FACEBOOK, INSTAGRAM, AND LINKEDIN

Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT

APPENDIX V: QUALTRICS SURVEY SNAPSHOT AS OF 9/25/20

mdxl.eu.qualtrics.com/Q/MyProjectsSection

CrushingPower.com Ernst & Young : Glo... Microsoft Office Ho... Homeport | RCL em... FVRs APS Client Share SPARK: M

Last 30 days

Survey	Status	Questions	Responses
LIGroup: "Including 'Choice' into Change Models via... Modified Sep 5, 2020	Active	24	7
FBGroup: "Including 'Choice' into Change Models vi... Modified Sep 5, 2020	Active	24	8
MGroup: "Including 'Choice' into Change Models via... Modified Sep 5, 2020	Active	24	23
PGroup: "Including 'Choice' into Change Models via... Modified Sep 5, 2020	Active	24	9

APPENDIX W: JOHN'S HOPKINS COVID-19 CASE REPORTING AS OF 9/25/20

Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT

APPENDIX Y: RCL CARES SALES TRAINING PERFORMANCE RESULTS APR TO SEPT 2020

APPENDIX Z: TRANSCRIBED INTERVIEWS

File Home Share View

Clipboard: Pin to Quick access, Copy, Paste, Copy path, Paste shortcut

Organize: Move to, Copy to, Delete, Rename

New: New Item, Easy access, New folder

Open: Properties, Edit, History

Select: Select all, Select none, Invert selection

OneDrive > Middlesex Masters Program > Module 7 > WBS4760 Ch 5 Data Analysis > INTERVIEW TRANSCRIPTION PARTICIPANT ID: 1000

Name	Status	Date modified
1000 Transcript FINAL	🔄	11/14/2020 5:11 PM
1001 Transcript FINAL	🟢	11/1/2020 5:54 PM
1002 Transcript FINAL	🟢	11/3/2020 4:27 PM
1003 Transcript Final	🟢	11/3/2020 4:47 PM
1004 Transcript Final	🟢	11/3/2020 5:04 PM
1005 Transcript Final	🟢	11/3/2020 5:22 PM
1006 Transcript Final	🟢	11/3/2020 5:31 PM
1007 Transcript FINAL	🟢	10/19/2020 10:00 PM
1008 TranscriptFinal	🟢	11/3/2020 6:13 PM
1010 Transcript Final	🟢	11/5/2020 4:52 PM
1013 Transcript FINAL	🟢	11/5/2020 5:11 PM
1014 Transcript FINAL	🟢	11/5/2020 5:34 PM
1015 Transcript FINAL	🟢	11/5/2020 6:19 PM
1016 Transcript Final	🟢	11/5/2020 6:48 PM
1018 Transcript FINAL	🟢	11/5/2020 7:01 PM

Interview Date: 9/1/20

You know?

OK, should be. Please share more. OK now we're recording OK.

Alright, so recording the interview. This is interview for ID number 1000.

Thank you so much for correcting me and we're conducting our interview today on my new model called scared. So let for the Masters program leading transformative change.

And so our questions today, the first one we want to do is to be able to review the model and have you had the opportunity Peter to review the scared. So what model? OK, very good that gives us permission so we can move forward with the interview.

Thank you. So the first question surrounds around simplicity. And in thinking of this reflecting on the model and your experience using the model, the scared quiz and the So what template? Let's discuss the following questions.

Including ‘Choice’ into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT

APPENDIX AA: PARTICIPATION MIX OF QUALITATIVE INTERVIEWS

Medium Structured Qualitative Interviews

Invitee Types - Invites	Count	Percentage	Full Transcripts Recorded	Count	Percentage
Academic	28	53.8%	Yes	15	58%
Masters Cohort	6	11.5%	No	0	0%
Cruise Colleague	18	34.6%	N/A	11	42%
Totals:	52	100%	Totals:	26	100%

Employee Status- Invites	Count	Percentage	Permission to Quote	Count	Percentage
Former Employee	1	4%	Yes	15	58%
Employee	7	27%	No	0	0%
External	18	69%	N/A	11	42%
Totals:	26	100%	Totals:	26	100%

Interview Status - Participants	Count	Percentage	Methodology	Count	Percentage
HELD	15	58%	Qualitative	15	58%
DECLINED	1	4%	Quantitative	0	0%
NOT HELD	10	38%	Mixed	0	0%
Totals:	26	100%	N/A	11	42%
			Totals:	26	100%

Interview Held Employee Status	Count	Percentage	Interview NOT Held Employee Status	Count	Percentage
Academic	4	26.7%	Academic	10	90.9%
Masters Cohort	3	20.0%	Masters Cohort	0	0.0%
Cruise Colleague	8	53.3%	Cruise Colleague	1	9.1%
Totals:	15	100%	Totals:	11	100%

APPENDIX AB: QUALTRICS SURVEY RESPONSES – PARTICIPANT DATA

Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT

APPENDIX AC: QUANTITATIVE DATA FROM QUALTRICS SURVEY RESPONSES

Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT

APPENDIX AD: NET PROMOTER SCORE

NPS Generator: <https://www.rentently.com/nps-calculator/>

- PROMOTERS
- PASSIVES
- DETRACTORS

22
16
5

Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT

APPENDIX AE: MAPPING OF THE INTERVIEW RESPONSES

Medium Structured Interview Outcomes									
Question	SIMPLE		HELPFUL			USABLE			Interviewee's Voice
ID #	1. How easy is the model to use?	2. Can you please state what each of the letters mean?	3. HELPFUL - SCARED	4. HELPFUL - SO WHAT	5. Would you be able to use this model on your own?	6. How would you use this model?	7. Would you use both parts together SCARED-SO WHAT?	8. How much more usable over the other?	KEY QUOTATION
1000	Understand concept	Indirectly could identify	Helpful - Change is not inevitable	you can't take ownership until you're your authentic self owns it. Excellent for coaching	yes	Taking Ownership is the most important part.	Yes	Both used together - excellent for coaching.	"The model is helpful. Change is not inevitable. Scared-So what puts you in the driver seat so you can question your way through it.", "The Power of Choice is taking ownership over change. Scared-So what helps you do that.", "Scared-So What can give you power over fear of change"
1001	Very Good - Easy to understand	Able to identify majority	I really understood what is possible.	This might be something that you could discover in a coaching scenario. This could be beneficial as a coaching tool and not just personal. Excellent for coaching.	Yes, because I've actually used it.	Can be used in personal, coaching or business.	Yes over time	Both used together over time. Helpful for personal and excellent for coaching.	"If you try to do the SO WHAT on its own, you're not dealing with the emotional aspects of change"
1002	Yes, Very easy to use.	Need a little practice.	I found it really helpful and wouldn't have done this normally. Keep Conflicted and Champion as they relate to both ends of the energy spectrum.	The words SO WHAT are great to ask so what will I do about the change. It follows logic. It is difficult at first but for me would be a "learned" model over time.	Difficult at first without learning how to use it...but then a good tool. I can use it on myself.	Definitely could be used as a coaching tool with learned use.	Yes, the thought process must be connected.	SCARED was more usable for me as it helped me to challenge my thinking about what mindset I am in towards change. And perhaps I was in the wrong mindset.	"The So What is so great because it challenges you to do something about the change.", "It's designed to give you permission to look at your feelings and then asks SO WHAT are you going to do about it?"
1003	Really Easy, simplistic, relevant, memorable	Able to identify each letter correctly.	Yes it does work as it incorporates the emotional positive and negative sides of change.	I think it's very helpful in taking ownership as a step process in developing a strategy towards change.	100% yes.	I've actually used this and feel that it's a great help for when change is imposed upon you or when change is happening to you.	I would use both together.	I have a stronger preference towards the SO WHAT as that is part of my personality - so what can I do. But then I can also use the SCARED as a reflection tool to understand the emotional side...and through reflection, help me to go forward.	"...each letter opens the door to reflection.", "As a coaching tool, it gives you a way forward - which is what coaching is all about."
1004	extremely easy and quite intuitive, relatable, fresh	Yes explained all letters accurately.	Yes it's very helpful. Especially the SCARED quiz. The questions are reflective of the change situation. My results were surprising that I was more positive than I originally thought.	So What is a little bit tricky. This part takes time. Very helpful but I want to be able to come back to it and work through it over time.	Yes, I'm using it now on myself and with my teams.	Would use it over time for reflection.	Yes but SCARED part first for reflection and then SO WHAT to be able to use over time. It's an evolution.	SCARED was more usable for me at the beginning. Need more time to reflect and build out the SO WHAT portion. SO WHAT is more about reflection and action. Needs time to develop.	"The SCARED part of the model, and the quiz, helped me to clarify my mindset and give me some breathing space to think a little bit about Myself- which I don't normally do.", "Other models are prescriptive and say this is how you are going to react, whereas this model gives you choice to be positive, neutral, or negative and that is more realistic. You do have a choice to make with change."
1005	Very easy - layout was very easy	SCARED all correct - SO WHAT not so much.	Helped me slow down and realize that change is a process.	My Favourite part. I like to go directly to the SO WHAT. It's very simple and helpful as a change plan.	Yes, because I've actually used it already on myself for a recent experience.	I'd like now to use it with my work team on situations that are occurring right now at work.	definitely. Use SCARED to tackle the emotional fear and then SO WHAT to fix it!	If you want the best outcome for change, use both together.	"SCARED-SO WHAT is a process that lets you stop and think about change", "The first part, SCARED, is so important because it allows you to work through change without all the emotion or preconceived bias. It gives you a new experience.", "I'm not a clinical psychologist but you might find you make the best decision."
1007	Very simple and easy to use in everyday life.	both parts correctly	Absolutely very helpful and easy to use.	Absolutely very helpful and easy to use.	Yes, and I've been using this already on myself.	I can use for small changes or for change that I anticipate is coming. Both in personal and work life.	Yes and no. You can use this on the "Fly" in real time to ask yourself questions about change in motion. In that instance you don't need both, but just the SCARED. And then later you can use SO WHAT. It's flexible.	The SCARED part for me is more useful. Not just helpful, but able to remember and use easily whenever change is implied.	
1008	It's very simple. I'm used to change models all my life and this is very simple.	At a glance not able but very memorable from a perspective of what it's meant to do.	very positive - very much could use as a coaching methodology	very positive - very much could use as a coaching methodology	Yes I can use on myself.	This is great to have a new tool in the toolbox to assess the challenges in life.	Certainly at times. YES	No. It just depends on the scenario and what needs and where you are in life.	"Wonderful tool that can be very useful because it takes change through bite size pieces and that can be helpful", "People are feeling overwhelmed and a model like this is the perfect framework towards a direction they might not otherwise have.", "Scared-So What is very clean, focused, easy to digest and makes sense. It's right there in center field."
1010	Quite easy to use. Responds to a need. Really useful.	Identified correctly	very helpful when you face a change	This is the model for me. I'm very visual. This is very helpful.	Clearly useable on myself.	Use at the beginning of a change to evaluate the feelings of where you are. Then focus on what can do about the change. I could also use as a coaching tool very easily.	The first part will help discover your feelings of where you are in the change. I prefer the second part the most because this relates to me and the type of person I am. I want to get into the detail of SO WHAT will I do. It's a planning template.	both parts	
1013	very simple and visual user friendly and helpful	Not able to remember	Very helpful to get in touch with my feelings. The quiz helped the most regardless of culture.	Helped me a lot. It's a guided conversation with myself.	Yes as I did use it on myself in a personal situation.	Definitely useable on myself as a coaching tool. Use on my teenager.	yes you have to as they flow together as a flexible model. Includes choice.	both parts	"It's a very important model specifically because it can be applied to both personal life and a professional work life as well."
1014	Easiness to use in everyday life. Work or personal	Remembers SCARED and later understood some of the SO WHAT	Yes this model will reflect on you.	Didn't find this as helpful at first as I'm a foreigner and didn't look too deeply. I need to revisit it. It takes time.	Yes and I have. I used it by myself and with friends.	Collaboratively with friends to foster the questions and discussion. Also could be better to use this as a coaching tool rather than a very expensive coach.	Scared part yes. Would like a little video tutorial for the SO WHAT portion.	Both and very helpful to use with groups of people together in talking with each other about situational change. Don't stop at the scared phase - go on and find out what to do about it.	"It's important to know you don't have to be scared to use this model. You can use for whatever type of situation you are in regardless of positive, neutral, or negative and no matter if it's personal or work related.", "You can use an expensive coach or you can use Scared So What and take control for your self."
1015	Very intuitive and very simple acronyms to remember. Amazing tool.	yes could explain correctly	Yes to understand feelings	Yes it's very detailed and good, but needs some tweaking. Need to add in the top add OBJECTIVE. Then add in People or Process section. Put in milestones to help people "Check" off steps along the way.	I can	I could but probably won't. I'm an experienced change agent. That said, yes, it's useful. And as a coaching tool.	use both parts together	Use both parts together	"This model can be trusted because it creates empathy straight out of the gate", "The schematic is linear but the model itself is not linear and it's excellent. Your journey can be positive or negative and that's what brings this home for me.", "As a mentoring tool, you could use this to help someone to solve for an objective they are having right then and there, within a business setting, that helps to develop them long term in their ability to hit their career objectives. And that's outstanding."
1016	Quite simple Pretty easy and simple to understand	Yes identified all correctly	Very helpful to identify and clarify the change.	Very helpful to identify and clarify the change.	Yes	Printed it out and have it on my desk to help me through work change. I will use with my team and leaders to help set an example of how to navigate the change process. Also very usable as a coaching tool.	yes both parts together. I need to do better at my feelings so the SCARED part is a good reminder.	For me so what...but both are equal.	"It's really a great way to take a deep breath before you get into the analytical part of the change. This helps you to ask yourself Am I going to be a part of the solution or am I going to reject it and move onto something else and not be involved with this change.", "As a coaching tool, it gets people to move on from the I don't know answers, to a model where I can now use to find out the answers"
1018	easy to use and sequential and comprehensive flexible	Yes identified all correctly	yes hits the nail right on the head. Love the questionnaire	The so what template is my favorite part to create actions.	Yes I can use on myself.	as a tool to support others for change. As a coaching tool.	they both go together.	both together	"As a practitioner, I think it's a great model to look change in the lens of the way they may be feeling. It can also be a great coaching tool."

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APPENDIX AF: EXCERPTS FROM KEN ROSS INTERVIEW

Ken Ross	President of Elisabeth Kubler-Ross Foundation
Question1	Do you believe that doctor Kuebler Ross ever intended for her model to be utilized in mainstream everyday business change processes?
Answer 1	<p>Initially, when she did it in 60s, immediately she thought it was just for dying patients. Very shortly thereafter, she realized that it was for all the staff and Families as well that came. I can't say exactly, but certainly within 18 months she realized that it applied to everyone, you know, going through grief and then from there it slowly kind of adapted.</p> <p>Over the years it became popular in popular media, of course. And it was just, I believe, before my mother passed, people started coming to her, asking her if this applied to business change or loss or anything like that and she said, well of course it applies to anyone going through any kind of change or loss.</p> <p>So yes, she knew about it. No, she didn't originally intend it. Certainly for business she was the most anti-business person you've ever met in your life really. She just wanted things to be simple, so yes she knew about it. Yes people came and discussed it with her. She said she had absolutely no problem with it. She said obviously you can apply it to 100 different situations. But no, that's not how I intended it. Obviously. I'm a doctor and trying to help dying patients with grief. With loss with change. So she did not apply to business, but she said it is intended for anyone going through loss or change. And it sounds like those are the keywords that you know. If it you know she intended for. If anybody wanted to use it, it was for loss of life or their loss through change. Because that would tie back to her her research in her career.</p>
Question2	Do you believe that doctor Kuebler Ross would have approved of her models being transcribed into the Sarah curve today? Which is shock anger resistance in acceptance and the reason I ask is because everything references the SARA curve back to her. However, I cannot find anything that she defines that she accepted that.
Answer 2	<p>Um, you know, she was had very little ego. She's like, you know, this is just supposed to be a part, a tool in a toolbox if you will. Or creating discussion because back in the 60s she was trying to build a bridge of vocabulary or build some kind of architecture that doctors could relate to their patients and vice versa because there was no common language spoken language that patients didn't understand and patients were all about emotions and feelings, which is something doctors are kind of trained. To ignore and not participate in. So what my mother is trying to do is build a bridge so they could have a common language. So she said this is great if you want to use it, use it. She said the problem with society, an immediate is that they've kind of portrayed the five stages as kind of solid, rigid thing and she said I'm just building a loose framework to frame the conversation. I never meant it to be 12345 people misrepresented, they say it's linear. You have to do this to graduate or to have acceptance. She said all this is nonsense. You don't have to go through the stages, I'm just trying to build this framework for conversation. But she said absolutely I'm not locked into this. If you want to add a six stages 10 modify it, that's great. I'm just trying to contribute to the conversation. I'm not saying I'm the only correct person or everyone goes through this, you know? So it's a loose framework and unfortunately that gets lost in society. And then they started attacking Elizabeth. Or something she never said and this matter of fact, if you look in the back of on death and dying, there's a chart. And in the chart there's ten stages. And yet in 50 years I've never heard one single article or any journalist mentioned Elizabeth ten stages.</p> <p>Wow, that's amazing.</p> <p>That wasn't caught in device. Right here. Grab a coffee. See if I can. I think it's wrong. Page 250 roughly. Here it is. So let me put that part of the camera there.</p> <p>Yes, I do have that. I do have that book so you can clearly see there's ten stages in the book from 1969.</p> <p>And they include things that people don't talk about at all. That's wrong, or other authors say, Oh well, Elizabeth didn't understand. There's a six stage. Hope you know, there's an entire entire chapter on hoping this book. It's already there, she wrote it. She wrote it. But people say always but don't realize. Hope is one of the stages, you know, so it or there are six stages. Elizabeth was wrong. I mean, it's ridiculous. So this preparatory grief, their shock. There's denial that partial denial. There's a lot of other things we talked about, so the five stages were meant to be like just the framework. I mean, there's she talked about as many as 13 different stages, she said. Obviously I'm simplifying it so that people can remember it were not in the field. If I make a complicated as it really is, no one would ever remember it. The point is, let's simplify it. Make it so that people on the street can remember it, and then it becomes useful if you make it too complicated is not useful, except maybe you know a researcher and that's not home addressing. I'm addressing the people who need. Help you were dying in a bed, yeah?</p> <p>That is so incredible and then just get overwhelmed with exciting feelings as well. When you say that because you're absolutely right, that's not taught. The rest of her stage is the 10 stages up to 13 as you mentioned. Nowhere is that discussed and then they attack Elizabeth because you know Elizabeth and her five stages. She just wants us to go through her five stages.</p> <p>And like, no, that's totally what she says even as early as 1975, she said. Let's get past The five stages, I mean that the conversations happen now. This is part of the reason is just so we could start a conversation it started so you know it's not an important part of my work, but everyone goes back to Elizabeth and the stages.</p> <p>Yeah, it sounds like she would just wanted to facilitate the conversation exactly which wasn't happening in the 60s and 70s.</p>

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APPENDIX AG: REC ETHICS APPROVAL FORM

Management, Leadership & Orgs REC

The Burroughs
Hendon
London NW4 4BT

Main Switchboard: 0208 411 5000

24/06/2020

APPLICATION NUMBER: 14390

Dear Grant Scott Van Ulbrich and all collaborators/co-investigators

Re your application title: Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SOWHAT

Supervisor: Chris Rigby

Co-investigators/collaborators:

Thank you for submitting your application. I can confirm that your application has been given APPROVAL from the date of this letter by the Management, Leadership & Orgs REC.

The following documents have been reviewed and approved as part of this research ethics application:

Document Type	File Name	Date	Version
Materials	SCARED SO WHAT MODEL GUV	09/04/2020	1
GDPR Declaration	Data Protection Declaration Form - Van Ulbrich	05/06/2020	1-Van Ulbrich
Data Protection Act checklist	(LSI) Data Protection Checklist (1) Van Ulbrich	05/06/2020	1- Van Ulbrich
Participant Information Sheet	Participant Information Sheet GUV INTERVIEWS	21/06/2020	6-21-20
Participant Information Sheet	MLO Consent Form GUV Interviews	21/06/2020	6.21.2020
Disclosure of Potential Conflict of Interest form	Conflict of Interest Form GUV	21/06/2020	6.21.2020
Resubmission Response to Feedback Summary	Resubmission Feedback Summary - Van Ulbrich Application 14390	21/06/2020	6.21.20

Although your application has been approved, the reviewers of your application may have made some useful comments on your application. Please look at your online application again to check whether the reviewers have added any comments for you to look at.

Also, please note the following:

1. Please ensure that you contact your supervisor/research ethics committee (REC) if any changes are made to the research project which could affect your ethics approval. There is an Amendment sub-form on MORE that can be completed and submitted to your REC for further review.
2. You must notify your supervisor/REC if there is a breach in data protection management or any issues that arise that may lead to a health and safety concern or conflict of interests.
3. If you require more time to complete your research, i.e., beyond the date specified in your application, please complete the Extension sub-form on MORE and submit it your REC for review.
4. Please quote the application number in any correspondence.
5. It is important that you retain this document as evidence of research ethics approval, as it may be required for submission to external bodies (e.g., NHS, grant awarding bodies) or as part of your research report, dissemination (e.g., journal articles) and data management plan.
6. Also, please forward any other information that would be helpful in enhancing our application form and procedures - please contact MOREsupport@mdx.ac.uk to provide feedback.

Good luck with your research.

Yours sincerely

Chair Dr Tim Freeman

Management, Leadership & Orgs REC

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APPENDIX AH: PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

MIDDLESEX UNIVERSITY

Participant Information Sheet (PIS)
More Than Minimal Risk or High Risk Projects

(Must be used with a Consent Form that is signed by participant and retained by the researcher) June 21, 2020

Participant ID Code:.....

SECTION 1

1. Project/Study title

Masters Module 7 Project: WBS4760: Title: “Including ‘Choice’ into Change Models via SCARED-SOWHAT: How do I explain change in a modern, simplistic, self-help model that incorporates personal choice and a support mechanism to see the change through?”

2. Invitation paragraph

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Ask us if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

Thank you for reading this.

3. What is the purpose of the study?

My aim is to give the SCARED-SO WHAT™ model to people by putting it out to our employees and to others externally for test and review. As Grant (2014) references, “The more you give, the more you want to do it – as do others around you.” Kurt Lewin also states, “People support what they create,” (Grabau and Swartz, 2013). These are key ingredients as I will want to give the models to others thus allowing them to support the creation and evolution of the SCARED-SO WHAT™ model.

My main objectives in doing this will be to achieve the following:

- Package the model into a user-friendly digestible presentation.
- Engage my employee base in reviewing, usefulness, and feedback.
- Introduce externally to my travel partner base for usefulness and feedback.
- Get the model published in a professional journal.

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- Collect data responses both quantitative and qualitative to assess feasibility and usefulness and or to change and adapt the model.

By performing these objectives, I should be in a position to assess feedback and incorporate into my final project dissertation and next steps.

4. Why have I been chosen?

It is important that we assess as many participants as possible, and you have indicated that you are interested in taking part in this study. You may be an internal employee of Royal Caribbean Cruises, Ltd and or a member of the master's program cohort or Consalia Ltd, or one of RCL's travel partners, or a professional colleague of whom I have chosen to include your thoughts and opinions into this research either via personal interview or via an online survey.

5. Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to take part, you are still free to withdraw without giving a reason. If you do decide to withdraw from the study then please inform the researcher as soon as possible, and they will facilitate your withdrawal. If, for any reason, you wish to withdraw your data please contact the researcher within 3 business days either in writing or via email or phone, of your participation. After this date it may not be possible to withdraw your individual data as the results may have already been published. However, as all data are anonymized, your individual data will not be identifiable in any way.

Please note: A decision to withdraw at any time, or a decision not to take part, will not affect your employment status with RCL in any way.

6. What will I have to do?

E.g. You will be asked to give answers to questions in an interview/questionnaire.

Of which should not take any longer than approximately 20 to 30 minutes for interviews and 5 to 10 min or surveys.

Please note that in order to ensure quality assurance and equity this project may be selected for audit by a designated member of the committee. This means that the designated member can request to see signed consent forms. However, if this is the case your signed consent form will only be accessed by the designated auditor or member of the audit team.

7. Will I have to provide any bodily samples (i.e. blood/saliva/urine)?

NO – does not apply

8. What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There are no known disadvantages nor risks in participating in this project. We hope that participating in the study will help you. However, this cannot be guaranteed. The

Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT

information we get from this study may help us to use the data from those sessions to help round out my research and frame up the change model accordingly. This research project will provide guidance to help further the development of the model and follows a socially constructed, subjective, approach. This may result in changing the model or strengthening its current format and structure.

9. What are the possible benefits of taking part?

There are no known risks in participating in this project. We hope that participating in the study will help you. However, this cannot be guaranteed. The information we get from this study may help us to use the data from those sessions to help round out my research and frame up the change model accordingly. This research project will provide guidance to help further the development of the model and follows a socially constructed, subjective, approach. This may result in changing the model or strengthening its current format and structure.

9. Will my taking part in this study be kept confidential?

The research team has put several procedures in place to protect the confidentiality of participants. You will be allocated a participant code that will always be used to identify any data you provide. Your name or other personal details will not be associated with your data, for example, the consent form that you sign will be kept separate from your data. All paper records will be stored in a locked filing cabinet, accessible only to the research team, and all electronic data will be stored on a password protected computer. All information you provide will be treated in accordance with the UK Data Protection Act.

*****NOTE: SEE SECTION 2 for research participant privacy notice*****

10. What will happen to the results of the research study?

The results of the research study will be used as part of an Postgraduate dissertation. The results may also be presented at conferences or in journal articles. However, the data will only be used by members of the research team and at no point will your personal information or data be revealed.

11. Who has reviewed the study?

The study has received full ethical clearance from the Research ethics committee who reviewed the study. The committee is the Business Research Ethics committee of Middlesex University in London, UK.

12. Contact for further information

If you require further information, have any questions or would like to withdraw your data then please contact:

Grant Van Ulbrich, Primary researcher via GV147@live.mdx.ac.uk

Including ‘Choice’ into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT

Or my research supervisor:

Chris Rigby, BA (Hons), PGCE, MBA, CMgr MCMI
Senior Lecturer (Practice)
Department of Management, Leadership & Organisations
Room W119, Williams Building
Middlesex University Business School
The Burroughs
Hendon
NW4 4BT
Tel: 0208 411 5431
E: c.rigby@mdx.ac.uk

Thank you for agreeing to take part in this study. You (the participant) should keep this “Participant Information with Consent” sheet since it contains important information and the research teams contact details.

SECTION 2

Middlesex University Privacy Notice for Research Participants

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) protects the rights of individuals by setting out certain rules as to what organisation can and cannot do with information about people. A key element to this is the principle to process individuals’ data lawfully and fairly. This means we need to provide information on how we process personal data.

The University takes its obligation under the GDPR very seriously and will always ensure personal data is collected, handled, stored and shared in a secure manner. The University’s Data Protection Policy can be accessed here:

https://www.mdx.ac.uk/_data/assets/pdf_file/0023/471326/Data-Protection-Policy-GPS4-v2.4.pdf.

The following statements will outline what personal data we collect, how we use it and who we share it with. It will also provide guidance on your individual rights and how to make a complaint to the Information Commissioner’s Officer (ICO), the regulator for data protection in the UK.

Why are we collecting your personal data?

As a university we undertake research as part of our function and in our capacity as a teaching and research institution to advance education and learning. The specific purpose for data collection on this occasion is to (See line item 3 in section 1).

The legal basis for processing your personal data under GDPR on this occasion is Article 6(1a) consent of the data subject.

Including ‘Choice’ into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT

Transferring data outside Europe

In the majority of instances your data will be processed by Middlesex University researchers only or in collaboration with researchers at other UK or European institutions so will stay inside the EU and be protected by the requirements of the GDPR.

In any instances in which your data might be used as part of a collaboration with researchers based outside the EU all the necessary safeguards that are required under the GDPR for transferring data outside of the EU will be put in place. You will be informed if this is relevant for the specific study you are a participant of.

Your rights under data protection

Under the GDPR and the DPA you have the following rights:

to obtain access to, and copies of, the personal data that we hold about you;

to require that we cease processing your personal data if the processing is causing you damage or distress;

to require us to correct the personal data we hold about you if it is incorrect;

to require us to erase your personal data;

to require us to restrict our data processing activities;

to receive from us the personal data we hold about you which you have provided to us, in a reasonable format specified by you, including for the purpose of you transmitting that personal data to another data controller;

to object, on grounds relating to your particular situation, to any of our particular processing activities where you feel this has a disproportionate impact on your rights.

Where Personal Information is processed as part of a research project, the extent to which these rights apply varies under the GDPR and the DPA. In particular, your rights to access, change, or move your information may be limited, as we need to manage your information in specific ways in order for the research to be reliable and accurate. If you withdraw from the study, we may not be able to remove the information that we have already obtained. To safeguard your rights, we will use the minimum personally-identifiable information possible. The Participant Information Sheet will detail up to what point in the study data can be withdrawn.

If you submit a data protection rights request to the University, you will be informed of the decision within one month. If it is considered necessary to refuse to comply with any of your data protection rights, you also have the right to complain about our decision to the UK supervisory authority for data protection, the Information Commissioner’s Office.

None of the above precludes your right to withdraw consent from participating in the research study at any time.

Including ‘Choice’ into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT

Collecting and using personal data

Personal data (e.g. your name, email address, voice or any data that can identify you) will NOT be collected by this study and your confidentiality will be protected. With your permission, interviews will be recorded and kept on my personal jump drive for continued reference and analysis during the study and for future research use.

Personal data is any data that can lead to the identification of a specific (living) person. It can be obviously identifiable data such as name or ID number but it can also be a combination of "innocent" data such as age, height/weight, wealth, job position, company, city, etc. that when combined can lead to the identification of a person.

Data sharing

Your information will usually be shared within the research team conducting the project you are participating in, mainly so that they can identify you as a participant and contact you about the research project.

Responsible members of the University may also be given access to personal data used in a research project for monitoring purposes and/or to carry out an audit of the study to ensure that the research is complying with applicable regulations. Individuals from regulatory authorities (people who check that we are carrying out the study correctly) may require access to your records. All of these people have a duty to keep your information, as a research participant, strictly confidential.

If we are working with other organisations and information is shared about you, we will inform you in the Participant Information Sheet. Information shared will be on a ‘need to know’ basis relative to achieving the research project’s objectives, and with all appropriate safeguards in place to ensure the security of your information.

Storage and security

The University takes a robust approach to protecting the information it holds with dedicated storage areas for research data with controlled access.

Alongside these technical measures there are comprehensive and effective policies and processes in place to ensure that users and administrators of University information are aware of their obligations and responsibilities for the data they have access to. By default, people are only granted access to the information they require to perform their duties. Training is provided to new staff joining the University and existing staff have training and expert advice available if needed.

Retention

Under the GDPR and DPA personal data collected for research purposes can be kept indefinitely, providing there is no impact to you outside the parameters of the study you have consented to take part in.

Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SO WHAT

Having stated the above, the length of time for which we keep your data will depend on a number of factors including the importance of the data, the funding requirements, the nature of the study, and the requirements of the publisher. Details will be given in the information sheet for each project.

Thank you for agreeing to take part in this study. You (the participant) should keep this "Participant Information with Consent" sheet since it contains important information and the research teams contact details.

APPENDIX AI: STATEMENT OF INFORMED CONSENT / CONFIDENTIALITY AGREEMENT

Participant Identification Number: _____

CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: Including 'Choice' into Change Models via SCARED-SOWHAT

Name of Researcher: Grant Van Ulbrich

Please initial box

1. I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet dated 6.21.2020 for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw within 3 business days, without giving any reason and without penalty.
3. I agree that this form that bears my name and signature may be seen by a designated auditor.
4. I agree that my non-identifiable research data may be stored in National Archives and be used anonymously by others for future research. I am assured that the confidentiality of my data will be upheld through the removal of any personal identifiers.
5. I understand that my interview may be video recorded and subsequently transcribed.
6. I agree to take part in the above study.

Name of participant

Date

Signature

Grant Van Ulbrich
Researcher

Aug 24, 2020
Date

Signature

1 copy for participant; 1 copy for researcher